

Council on Library Resources, Inc. 21st Annual Report 1977

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Library Resources, Inc.

**21st
Annual Report
1977**

One Dupont Circle
Washington, D.C. 20036

Acknowledgements

The scholar at his book-wheel on page 3 is a reproduction of an engraving in Agostino Ramelli's *Le diverse et artificiose machine . . .*, Paris: 1588. It first appeared in the Council's third annual report, which explained that "the picture symbolizes the interest of the Council on Library Resources in both the content of books and the mechanics of library service." It has appeared in each annual report since that time. Other photo credits are as follows:

- page 8 — cathode ray tube with cataloging data, courtesy of Colorado College, recipient of a 1977-1978 Library Service Enhancement Program (LSEP) grant.
- page 22 — library interior, courtesy of the University of Colorado, Colorado Springs, recipient of a 1977-78 LSEP grant.
- page 28 — library interior, again courtesy of Colorado College.
- page 36 — student using audiovisual equipment, again courtesy of the University of Colorado, Colorado Springs; student using book, courtesy of the University of Evansville, recipient of a CLR-NEH College Library Program grant.
- page 44 — student using microfiche reader, again courtesy of the University of Evansville; film display, courtesy of Glenville State College, recipient of a 1977-78 LSEP grant.
- page 50 — Robert Vosper, CLR board member, addressing conference participants at IFLA's 50th Anniversary Congress in Brussels in September 1977, courtesy of IFLA.

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June 30, 1977

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The Year 1976–1977

LAST YEAR IN OUR 20TH ANNUAL REPORT we took the opportunity afforded by the anniversary to review the events of CLR's first two decades of operation. In that context it was easy to see the strides that librarians and their associates had taken toward solving some of their more pressing problems. This report covering CLR's 21st year has a narrower focus, but further consolidation and progress can be seen in several important areas. A national library and information service network appears to be taking on more definite shape. A national program for preserving library materials has been initiated. The model Academic Library Development Program has moved into a new phase of testing and refinement. The Consortium for Public Library Innovation took up where the College Entrance Examination Board's Office of Independent Study and Guidance Projects left off in facilitating innovative public library programs for adult independent study. Seventeen institutions of higher education began projects intended to make their libraries more active partners in the academic process, four under the revised College Library Program, and thirteen with the assistance of Library Service Enhancement Program grants. And with the approval of its members the International Federation of Library Associations committed itself to an ambitious program of professional library work that crosses national borders and incorporates the Third World.

The Council has been involved with all of these activities and more, as described in the following pages. During the year that ended June 30, 1977, 72 projects were active, 34 of them requiring new allocations totaling \$1,306,854. The year also marked a change in the Council's funding structure. Beginning July 1, 1977, support for the Council will no longer be furnished solely by the Ford Foundation but will be shared also by other foundations. It seems appropriate at this time to express again our deep gratitude to the Ford Foundation for its continued assistance to the Council and thus to the library world over the past 21 years.

Fred C. Cole
President

The Growth of a National Library System

FOR YEARS librarians and information scientists have spoken with a mixture of pride and despair of the explosion of knowledge that has continued unabated since the end of World War II. Technology has given us a window on the universe, one seemingly shrunk in size but so grown in complexity that information and knowledge have become necessities for advancement and even for survival. Provision of these commodities has therefore become a valued service in modern society. With the burgeoning of print and nonprint material in the twentieth century, librarians and scholars may no longer take comfort in the traditional belief of the past century that "within these marble walls resides the knowledge of mankind." Instead, they must turn to their advantage a world increasingly bound by unseen webs of electronic impulses and dominated by blips of green light dancing across television-like screens. It is not always an easy transition.

In the mid-1950s, when the Council on Library Resources was created, technology was seen as the key to regaining control over the expanding realm of knowledge—if it could be harnessed to work for libraries. During the next 15 years academic libraries in the United States enjoyed a great period of growth and affluence as college enrollments spiraled upward and monies from private and federal sources poured into university coffers. This resulted in more funded research and expanded curricula, development of greater library collections to support them, hiring of additional staff to service the collections, and so on. Federal legislation also provided additional funds for public and school libraries, enabling them to serve more people than ever before. Although finding the right way to apply technology to library processes seemed to be taking longer and costing more than early optimism had warranted, the development of MEDLARS (Medical Literature Analysis and Retrieval System) at the National Library of Medicine and the MARC (Machine-Readable Cataloging) project at the Library of Congress nevertheless made it technically feasible to think in terms of the creation of truly national resources to be shared by libraries and their users throughout America.

In the 1960s even though they were enjoying more support and operating more efficiently than ever before, libraries still could not keep up with the flood of information, increasingly in nonprint forms, that poured from U. S. and foreign publishers. In the last five years the problem has become critical, for now it is painfully clear that a period of affluence has ended. Reduced budgets, declining enrollments, inflationary costs, the energy crisis, and other social and political problems have brought about a period of severe retrenchment for libraries. Yet the demand for service remains high.

Louis B. Wright, director emeritus of the Folger Shakespeare Library, pointed out to the members of the Association of Research Libraries last fall that their very effectiveness had created demands that threatened to swamp them. "Scientists, social workers, historical scholars, writers, humanists of every type are descending upon the research libraries in

ever-increasing numbers with requests for source material and information infinite in variety. . . . Every learned discipline may have a vast literature of printed books, specialized periodicals, statistical reports, abstracts, graphs, pictorial reports, even sound tracks and records, not to mention storage banks of information in computerized forms. The acquisition of all this material is costly, time-consuming, and space devouring. . . . No longer can even the richest university research library hope to be complete and self-sufficient in all fields of knowledge."¹ Somehow the costs of operating these singular institutions must be reduced even while their services are improved.

By 1970, after years of careful study of the complexities of reducing the unit costs of operating libraries, the Council, the National Commission on Libraries and Information Science (NCLIS), and others had concluded that the solution lay in the development of a national library and information system that would facilitate the sharing of resources and eliminate wasteful duplication of effort. In order to share resources successfully, each library or other repository in the system needs to know what has been published and who owns it. Each item must therefore be described in terms of its intellectual content (i.e., what is it about?) and its physical properties (i.e., is it a book, film, cassette?). This information becomes a bibliographic record, which can then be distributed by itself on a catalog card or with others in a book or on magnetic tape. To each record can be added a call number, indicating where the piece can be found within a specific collection, or a location symbol, telling which particular libraries or library systems own it. Thus the first step in creating a national library and information system must be development of a comprehensive, economical, cooperative method of preparing acceptable bibliographic records and making them readily available, on a machine-readable or manual basis, to all libraries: a system of national bibliographic control. The key to its achievement is the merging of the nation's bibliographic records into a national bibliographic data base that can be used by all the various nodes that make up the national library and information system for whatever purposes will satisfy local and regional needs.

Much of the Council's 1976–1977 activity associated with the emerging national system began some years ago.² A full understanding of the events of fiscal year 1977 requires that they be set briefly in the context of the recent past.

Committee for the Coordination of National Bibliographic Control

For the past three years a committee composed of representatives from the library, publishing, information dissemination, and abstracting and indexing service worlds has pursued a program of action designed to

1. Louis B. Wright. "Our Cultural Heritage: Whence Salvation?" *Research Libraries and the Bicentennial*, Minutes of the Eighty-Ninth Meeting, October 20–21, 1976. Association of Research Libraries (Washington, 1977), p. 13.
2. For an overview of the Council's first 20 years of operation, consult CLR's *20th Annual Report*.

bring those communities closer to a coherent system of bibliographic control. Sponsored by the Council, the National Science Foundation, and the National Commission on Libraries and Information Science, the six-member Committee for the Coordination of National Bibliographic Control (CCNBC) identifies the major obstacles preventing the development of such a system, then enlists a small army of qualified professionals to work on removing them.³ Council staff members act as chairman and executive secretary for the group.

In the past year several committee projects have been completed and substantive work has begun on three others. The Working Party on Bibliographic Name Authority Files and the Working Party on Formats for Journal Articles and Technical Reports have submitted their findings to the committee for analysis and review. Likewise, a study on the current and potential uses of the International Standard Book Number (ISBN) in libraries has been completed. Upon acceptance and final editing of the reports, CCNBC hopes to make them widely available to the information community.

In order to examine some of the more difficult problems, the CCNBC will on occasion initiate a series of planning meetings to determine the most effective method of investigation. The complexity of issues surrounding the use of optical scanning technology (e.g., bar codes, optical character recognition [OCR] fonts, magnetic stripes, and the like) seemed to call for this approach. Accordingly, a small group known as the Planning Committee on Automated Identification Systems (AIDS) met on several occasions to consider the many and varied symbologies that have emerged and their impact on each sector of the information community. Planning committee members commissioned a brief study and prepared a background paper for a colloquium held in January 1977 during the midwinter conference of the American Library Association. Committee members are now developing a strategy to continue the momentum gained from this meeting.

Toward the end of the fiscal year CCNBC turned its attention to current methods of providing subject access to information. The problems encountered by many users in searching for specific information have been compounded by the growing number of computerized indexing services and machine-readable data bases, each one different in its method of subject analysis. A workshop approach to the situation, similar to that used in the AIDS investigation, is planned.

Because its members realize that national bibliographic control cannot be achieved without adoption of acceptable standards, CCNBC keeps in close touch with the work of the American National Standards Institute, the National Bureau of Standards, and other agencies, to which questions in their purview are referred when appropriate.

3. XX:27-29. Citations in this form refer to the Council's annual reports: for example, to the *20th Annual Report*, pages 27-29, which contain a detailed account of how this committee came into being.

THE REQUIREMENT FOR STANDARDS

It appears certain that any national system will have to be based on a cooperative effort that depends on the sharing of records as well as information about those records by the producers and maintainers of the system. This sharing cannot come about without a common understanding of the intellectual content of the records and a common agreement on their organization—in short, without nationally accepted standards.

The Council has for many years pressed for the development and voluntary adoption of codes, definitions, rules, and procedures as a necessary step in the evolution of a national library system. In the United States the administrative responsibility for voluntary standards work reposes in the American National Standards Institute (ANSI), a federation of more than 160 technical, professional, and trade organizations and 1,000 companies. Since 1960 CLR, together with the National Science Foundation, has supported the work of ANSI's Committee Z/39, which is responsible for preparing voluntary standards in the area of library work, documentation, and related publishing practices.⁴

During fiscal year 1977 Committee Z/39 completed work on five new standards that were later approved by ANSI for publication. They dealt with the structure for representing names of countries for information interchange, romanization of Cyrillic characters, form of bibliographic reference, a format for scientific and technical translations, and identification codes for use by the bibliographic community. The committee is also active in international standards work; it is the representative of ANSI to the ISO (International Organization for Standardization) Technical Committee 46 on Documentation.

Revision of *Anglo-American Cataloging Rules*

A code that has been adopted by most libraries in the United States, Canada, Great Britain, and a number of other countries is the *Anglo-American Cataloging Rules (AACR)*. Published in 1967, the widely used systematic set of rules controls the choice of entry (e.g., whether a treaty should be listed primarily under the names of the countries involved or under its own name), the form of heading (e.g., whether *Benedictines* or the order's less familiar ancient Latin name should be used), and the physical descriptions of library materials. In 1975 the Council made an award to the American Library Association (ALA) on behalf of the Joint Steering Committee for the Revision of the *AACR*, composed of representatives from ALA, the Canadian Committee on Cataloguing, the [British] Library Association, the British Library, and the Library of Congress.⁵ The move toward revision grew out of a need to take into account developments since 1967, such as international standards promulgated in recent years and new categories of nonprint materials (slides, graphics, cassettes, and

4. XX:34–35.

5. XIX:13; XX:35.

the like) that now form a substantial part of library collections. This year the Joint Steering Committee requested and received additional funds to carry the work through August 1977. It is expected that the manuscript will be completed and published soon thereafter. An important step in promoting acceptance of the revised code was taken when the Library of Congress announced that it will adopt the revised rules when it closes its card catalog in 1980.

THE LIBRARY OF CONGRESS AS THE NATIONAL BIBLIOGRAPHIC CENTER

The decision of the Library of Congress (LC) to adopt the revised *AACR*, thereby ending its practice of occasionally superimposing its own rules when necessary, is an important one, for in the Council's view the Library is the key node in any national library and information system. Its central position rests not only on the vastness of its collections (72.6 million pieces in 1976) but on the nearly uniform acceptance in the library world of its cataloging, in both content and format, as *de facto* standards. Since the early part of the century LC has distributed its printed catalog cards to libraries here and abroad. Since the late 1960s it has also delivered the data in machine-readable form through the MARC Distribution System. But the Library has not been able to include all possible library materials within its system, nor can it ever be expected to carry the burden alone; politically and economically such complete coverage is beyond reach. Therefore there must be among other institutions an acceptable division of labor, responsibility, and authority for the creation of those records required by libraries but not produced by LC. Two important projects, CONSER and COMARC, are testing the feasibility of decentralizing the labor in this manner while maintaining record quality.

CONSER

Much has been written about the CLR-managed and -funded CONSER (Conversion of Serials) project, a cooperative file-building effort initiated four years ago to develop a national data base of serials records.⁶

The data base resides at the Ohio College Library Center (OCLC). Under a contract with CLR that runs through November 1977, OCLC has enhanced its computer programs to accommodate the data base. Fourteen libraries now participate in the project by contributing additional records to the basic data base, composed of the Minnesota Union List of Serials and the machine-readable files of the Library of Congress and the National Library of Canada. The Library of Congress and the National Library of Canada are also charged with the responsibility of "authenticating" the records; they approve the bibliographic content and make sure that the appropriate key title and International Standard Serial Number

6. XX:24-25.

(ISSN) have been assigned. Other CONSER participants are the Boston Theological Institute, Cornell University, the Department of Interior, Harvard University, the National Agricultural Library, the National Library of Medicine, the New York State Library, the State University of New York, the University of California's University-Wide Library Automation Program, the University of Florida (Gainesville), the University of Minnesota, and Yale University. The CONSER data base has been further enhanced by grants from the National Endowment for the Humanities (NEH) and the National Science Foundation (NSF) for the entry of additional serial records in the humanities and in science and technology. The National Federation of Abstracting and Indexing Services has also contributed to the NSF-funded effort.

Of the estimated 200,000–300,000 records eventually to be contained in the data base, over 170,000 have thus far been contributed and 64,000 have been authenticated. LC, OCLC, and CONSER staff are collaborating on improving the system for handling and delivery of the CONSER records.

Two CLR systems specialists have devoted full time to the project since it began. In 1975 the Council made additional funds available through a grant to the Library of Congress for planning the second phase of the project (known as CONSER II), which involves moving CONSER to the LC computer system. The Library plans to assume eventual responsibility for the management of CONSER and will continue the service it began in July 1976 of providing authenticated CONSER records through its MARC Distribution System. In a recent article the CONSER Continuation Team, composed of LC and CLR staff, reported that the goals of CONSER II "will be to: (1) improve the bibliographic control of serials across institutions; (2) promote the use of unique identifiers (key title and ISSN) by libraries and other secondary information services such as abstracting and indexing services and publishers; and (3) improve the accumulation of and the access to location information for more effective interlibrary loan and resource sharing."⁷

COMARC

The second experimental project in decentralizing labor is COMARC (Cooperative MARC), first funded by the Council in 1974 and centered at the Library of Congress.⁸ With the assistance of the grant the Library accepts machine-readable records created locally by selected U.S. libraries which base their work on LC cataloging copy derived from printed cards, proof sheets, and entries in the *National Union Catalog*. LC then removes the duplicates, compares the records for accuracy with its official catalog, updates them for consistency when required, and disseminates them through the MARC Distribution Service. Approximately 22,000

7. Henriette D. Avram and Richard Anable. "The Next Generation of CONSER." *American Libraries* 8 (1977):23.

8. XX:25–26.

records had been distributed in this fashion as of June 1977. Current COMARC participants are the 3-M Company—Library Systems, Northwestern University, University of Chicago, Washington State Library, Yale University, Boston Theological Institute, Cornell University, Smithsonian Institution, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign, University of Tennessee at Knoxville, and University of Wisconsin at Madison (the latter seven through the Ohio College Library Center).

Like CONSER, the project demonstrates a concept critical to the development of a national bibliographic data base: a machine-readable data base can be constructed from records supplied by many agencies, thus eliminating wasteful duplication of effort and allowing for faster growth and greater currency. At the same time record quality and consistency can be maintained through the efforts of a designated central bibliographic authority. In this case the authority is the Library of Congress, whose staff ensure that the records are accurate and that duplicates are eliminated. In January 1977 the Council made a second grant, this time for \$55,000, to provide for additional project personnel.⁹ A total of \$149,632 has been allocated by the Council to this important experiment in cooperation.

NETWORKS COME OF AGE

CONSER and COMARC provide positive evidence of the benefits of a division of labor in developing facets of the growing national system. Cooperation is necessary not only in terms of the labor required to develop such a system, but also because of the great costs involved in applying computer technology to manual systems. Except for a few of the largest institutions, most libraries are unable to support a computer system dedicated to their exclusive use. Only through the formation of various kinds of consortia or networks have they been able to take advantage of automated procedures. The need for libraries to share expenses as well as labor has become even more critical in the last five years because of the stringent financial condition of most educational institutions. Consequently, various agencies have created networks or systems to solve local or regional pieces of the problem. What had been lacking until recently, however, is a coordinated national approach to ensure that a flexible confederation of library systems will develop and work toward the common goal of creating a truly comprehensive national bibliographic system.

Last year it was determined that the time had come to bring representatives of the major library networks together to lay the groundwork for planning the bibliographic component of a national library and information service network. Beginning in April 1976 the Council supported a series of meetings at the Library of Congress at which the directors of major networks explored the requirements and possibilities for increased cooperation. In August 1976 the directors' group was asked to act in an

9. "COMARC Project Continues." *CLR Recent Developments* 5 (March 1977):2.

advisory capacity to the newly created LC Network Development Office and became known as the Network Advisory Group (NAG). During the year covered by this report NAG prepared a working paper that outlined the goals, assumptions, objectives, and functions of a national library and information service network and its library bibliographic component.¹⁰ It also listed the tasks that in the group's judgment are necessary to develop the component, assigned priorities to them, and began a program of action to complete them. The preliminary document was issued in June 1977 and disseminated for comment to the membership and governing boards of the organizations involved as well as to others in the fields of libraries and information science. It is planned that the report in its final form will become an official recommendation to the Library of Congress and to the National Commission on Libraries and Information Science from NAG, which in April 1977 was designated the Network Advisory Committee to the Librarian of Congress.

A new Council grant made in February will support meetings through 1977 of both NAG and a subgroup, the Network Technical Architecture Group (NTAG). NTAG is composed of technical experts from the major networks; its concern is with the nuts and bolts of linking the various bibliographic systems to the Library of Congress and to each other. Funds were obtained from the Committee for the Coordination of National Bibliographic Control for one of NTAG's projects: a study of the standardized query text format, response text format, and other formats for error messages and for control of information within a machine-readable message text.

In addition to the Library of Congress and the Council on Library Resources, members of the Network Advisory Committee¹¹ represent the American Library Association, AMIGOS Bibliographic Council, Association of Research Libraries, BALLOTS (Stanford University), Bibliographic Center for Research, California Library Authority for Systems and Services, Council for Computerized Library Networks, Federal Library Committee, Mideast Region Library Network, National Commission on Libraries and Information Science, National Library of Medicine, New England Library Information Network, Ohio College Library Center, Research Libraries Group, Southeastern Library Network, University of Chicago, and Washington (State) Library Network.

Ohio College Library Center

Certainly the largest network in operation today radiates from the Ohio College Library Center (OCLC) in Columbus, Ohio.¹² Begun in the

10. Library of Congress Network Advisory Group. *Toward a National Library and Information Service Network: The Library Bibliographic Component*, preliminary ed. (Washington, 1977).

11. When the Network Advisory Group was officially appointed as the Library of Congress Network Advisory Committee, its membership was expanded to include representatives of the organizations indicated. However, the committee continues to be known informally and in print by its earlier name and acronym (NAG).

12. XX:29-30.

early 1970s as a system for Ohio libraries, the center now serves over 900 libraries in 46 states and the District of Columbia. At June 30, 1977, its on-line union catalog contained over 2.9 million catalog records and 14 million location listings. Participating libraries now catalog approximately 200,000 books per week on the system. Over 90 percent of the time the records required for cataloging purposes are found in the OCLC data base.

OCLC completed work under its fourth CLR grant in May 1977 and reported that the development of an automated acquisitions subsystem, a study of authority files, and the installation of a subject retrieval capability had been accomplished. When fully implemented the acquisitions subsystem will provide member libraries with the capacity to keep a separate on-line order file and also share bibliographic information contained in that file with other libraries. After searching to determine whether an item is already on hand or on order, a library will be able to use the system to prepare order forms automatically and send them to vendors. Additional capabilities will include fund accounting and issuing claims for unfilled orders. The information gathered in a grant-supported survey of the current acquisitions policies, procedures, and practices of OCLC participants will assist the center in completing work on the acquisitions subsystem.

As 1976 drew to a close, the Council made a fifth grant to OCLC of \$122,000 for a study of the future governance and organization of the center by the consulting firm of Arthur D. Little, Inc. The study was commissioned by the OCLC Advisory Council, a group established by the OCLC Board of Trustees and comprising 13 individuals from librarianship, science, business, and government. The study results will guide the advisory council in its recommendations to the OCLC board and membership.

BALLOTS

Another bibliographic system that has expanded beyond its place of origin is BALLOTS (Bibliographic Automation of Large Library Operations using a Time-Sharing System), which was initially developed to support technical processing (acquisitions and cataloging) in the Stanford University Libraries.¹³ In the three years following its 1972 genesis the system broadened to permit searching and cataloging by seven California public libraries and later by other institutions both in and out of California. As of June 1977 its data base contained over 830,000 records. In addition to the Council, the U.S. Office of Education and the National Endowment for the Humanities have supported BALLOTS' development.

In 1975, a second joint grant from the Council and NEH allowed the BALLOTS Center to undertake further design and development in order

13. XX:31.

to make the system even more usable as a network by libraries other than Stanford. Tasks to be accomplished included improving the design of the files that make up the data base as well as designing a new video terminal to support an expanded MARC character set, programming the terminal, and then working it into the system. At the close of fiscal year 1977 BALLOTS reported that the programming and testing of the new Zentec terminal were completed. Work is scheduled to begin shortly on a manual for users of the terminal.

The University of Chicago's Library Data Management System

Like the BALLOTS system at Stanford University, the Library Data Management System at the University of Chicago was originally conceived as a comprehensive system for the use of one institution. CLR has supported the system's development since 1970 in cooperation with the National Endowment for the Humanities.¹⁴ A third CLR award, the second matched by NEH, was made to the university this year. The new grant, which totals \$326,925, supports work on three major tasks: catalog control, to allow for implementation of an on-line authority system; development of a quadraplanar structure for the data base; and completion of a general circulation system.

A stated goal of the Chicago effort has been to share the results of its systems development with other libraries. Its staff members are currently holding discussions with research libraries in the area to determine the feasibility of establishing a cooperative network. Recently the university library received a grant from the Joseph and Helen Regenstien Foundation for expansion of its minicomputer facilities, a key factor in enhancing the potential for sharing its system.

NELINET, MIDLNET, and the Washington State Library

CLR has contributed to the development of most of the existing major networks in a variety of ways. In cases such as those described above, the financial support has been substantial. In others the assistance has been primarily consultative, and in still others small sums have been granted for specific tasks. A grant this year to the Washington State Library to cover costs of a circulation system study falls into this latter category. The 140-page report prepared by Blackwell North America, Inc. provides a detailed analysis of the comparative costs and feasibility of central versus distributed computer operations for the Washington Library Network (WLN) circulation system. Since many network agencies are or soon will be facing the question of how to provide an effective automated circulation system for their members, this grant was made in the hope that the results would be useful elsewhere as well as to WLN. Assistance also was given this year to the relatively new Midwest Region Library Network (MIDLNET) for the services of a technical advisor and to the New England

14. XX:32.

Library Information Network (NELINET) for publication of a survey designed to determine the impact of the OCLC system on the internal workings of NELINET member libraries.

Regional Cooperation in the West

In 1975 CLR made a grant to the Western Interstate Commission for Higher Education (WICHE) to design and implement an interstate bibliographic network in 17 western states and British Columbia.¹⁵ According to the final project report it was eventually determined that existing organizations (e.g., the Washington Library Network, AMIGOS Bibliographic Council, the Bibliographical Center for Research) were capable of providing operational support for networking, thus eliminating any need for a separate broker of computer-based services. However, no group other than the Western Council of State Librarians, the overseers of WICHE's library program, was in a position "to coordinate state and multistate research, analysis, plans, policies, and continuing education for library resource sharing."¹⁶ In April 1976 the WICHE library program was renamed the Western Interstate Library Coordinating Organization (WILCO) and was redirected "to offer a forum for investigating regional library concerns, to catalyze and facilitate interstate resource sharing, and to coordinate regional interests with national library network planning."¹⁷

At the conclusion of the CLR grant in September 1976 the Western Council of State Librarians voted to continue and substantially increase funding for the coordinating staff so that it might carry out programs and tasks identified throughout the course of the grant. These are outlined in a planning document entitled "Library Networking in the West: The Next Three Years" that has been circulated to the western library community for review and comment. The following April the western state librarians voted to retire the name of WILCO, to move from under the WICHE umbrella and set up a separate organization, and to continue their activities as the independent Western Council of State Libraries.

MINITEX Plans Serials Location System

One of the keys to successful resource sharing is the ability of library users anywhere in the country to identify the institutions that own the specific materials they require. This is especially critical with regard to serials — magazines, journals, and the like — for they are difficult to safeguard and so numerous that no library can own a truly comprehensive collection. Location information for serials is currently found in hundreds of local, state, and regional union lists of serials. These lists,

15. XIX:14; XX:32.

16. Karl M. Pearson, Jr. and Eleanor A. Montague. *The Founding of the Western Interstate Library Coordinating Organization: A Narrative Final Report on the Project "Initiating the Design and Development of a Western Interstate Bibliographic Network."* (Boulder, Colo., 1976), p. 1.

17. *Ibid.*

many of which are outdated, have been compiled at a tremendous cost. Since they vary widely in such matters as format or interpretation of cataloging rules, most of them cannot be easily combined. A national system of serials locations would lessen the need for costly and duplicative manual efforts, thus releasing funds for more productive library uses.

A CLR grant of \$25,000 was awarded this year to MINITEX (Minnesota Interlibrary Telecommunications Exchange), a cooperative agency that facilitates resource sharing for Minnesota libraries, to enable it to plan a pilot project that could serve as an initial component of a national serials location system.¹⁸ The project calls for certain local and regional serials holdings statements to be linked to records in the CONSER file. This should provide library users with more efficient physical access to the journals they need at a lower cost to the libraries involved. The Library of Congress and the Indiana Cooperative Library Service Agency (IN-COLSA) also participate in the project.

OTHER AUTOMATION PROJECTS

Council support for automation projects has not been limited to large libraries or networks. Funds have been provided for other experiments in adapting technology to library processes that show promise of contributing to overall development in the field. A small grant made this year to John H. Gribbin, director of libraries at the University of Missouri — Columbia, for example, will enable him to undertake a study of the substitution of cooperatively maintained data bases for library card catalogs.

Improved Subject Access

CLR made a grant last year to the Syracuse University School of Information Studies for a project that attempts to demonstrate that subject access to monographs can be improved by augmenting MARC records.¹⁹ Working with a sample of approximately 2000 books in the humanities and social sciences, the project staff has enlarged the MARC record for each book by including as additional subject descriptors words and phrases found in the index and/or table of contents. The file of descriptors for the books in the sample has been processed by the System Development Corporation's ORBIT (On-line Retrieval of Bibliographic Information—Time-shared) Search Service, and on-line computer-based subject searches have been made by project staff and others who have access to the service. A six-month extension to December 1977 has been granted for additional analysis and evaluation in order to determine whether such enriched records contribute significantly to the improved performance of on-line computer subject searches for monographs.

18. *CLR Recent Developments* 5 (March 1977):4.

19. XX:33–34.

This year a second grant in the area of subject access went to Iowa State University for a project to develop mechanized indexing procedures that can be applied to the production of a subject-enhanced keyword index. The project focuses on data entry and descriptor selection procedures that can be generally applied to any academic or research library reference collection, or indeed any other component of a library collection. A specific result of the project will be the generation in hard copy and microfiche of a subject index to the Iowa State University Library reference collection of approximately 9,000 titles.

On-Line Reference Service Using PLATO

A pilot study of the feasibility of using the PLATO (Programmed Logic for Automated Teaching Operations) computer system to provide reference service when professional librarians are not available was carried out at the library of the University of Illinois College of Law.²⁰ This initial experiment focused on the use of government publications, since these are found in many types of libraries. Through a system of programmed instruction a user can now use a PLATO terminal to learn about various state and federal documents and where they fit into the process of developing a legislative history. The user can also call up a library floor plan indicating the particular shelf that contains the item sought. The program has been so written that any institution with access to PLATO facilities, even if there are no skilled programmers on its staff, can establish this service capability by simply substituting its own floor plans and other specific information on library materials in its collection.

Computer Use of *Books for College Libraries*

A small grant to Stockton State College in Pomona, New Jersey, supports an experimental use of the second edition of *Books for College Libraries (BCL II)*. Published by the American Library Association in 1975 with financial assistance from the Council, *BCL II* is a catalog of the 40,000 basic titles any four-year liberal arts college should have in its library if it intends to provide students with an adequate education. Many libraries used the first edition, also produced with CLR aid, to check their holdings in order to assess coverage of specific subject areas.

Computerized techniques were used to produce the new edition of *Books for College Libraries*, which is available from ALA on machine-readable tape as well as in book form.²¹ Since the Stockton State College library's holdings are also in machine-readable form, a computer will be used to match the collection against the recommended titles. Lists generated in this fashion could also be used for accreditation purposes, for ordering, or for circulation studies.

20. XX:33.

21. XX:56-57.

Library Management

IN A "NATIONAL INVENTORY OF LIBRARY NEEDS, 1975" prepared by the National Commission on Libraries and Information Science (NCLIS), it was estimated that American school, public, and academic libraries annually cost over \$3 billion to operate.²² Approximately one third of this amount is invested in academic and research libraries, a rise of over 367 percent in 10 years. Now, however, increasing support for libraries appears to be a thing of the past. The 1976 operating statistics for the 94 university library members of the Association of Research Libraries (ARL) showed that during that year 46 percent received either no budgetary increase or one that did not equal the rise in the consumer price index.²³

Increases in periodical subscription rates dramatically illustrate the fiscal bind in which academic research libraries find themselves. By far the most expensive journals are those in science and technology, and they also show the most alarming increases. Physics journals, for example, which cost an average of \$48.55 per subscription in 1967, now average \$165.71 and range as high as \$1540.80 for a single title!²⁴ If budgets fail to keep pace—and in 70 percent of the ARL libraries surveyed above they did not—then some other part of the library's collection or service must suffer. According to one reporter, departmental libraries in science and technology are already spending over 80 percent of their book budgets on journals and other serials.²⁵ If as all of this evidence suggests research libraries face the future with less money and reduced purchasing power, the need for good management and fiscal practices, important even in the best of times, is underscored.

In 1968 the Council determined that the achievement of management excellence by libraries was a matter of high priority and would be best accomplished by the formulation of a long-range program. Early grants, described in detail in previous annual reports, resulted in an influential study of management practices in large university libraries, followed by a case study of aspects of management in a specific institution, the Columbia University Libraries.²⁶ This in turn led to the establishment of Columbia University's Libraries Planning Office, which received CLR support for its first three years. A library research and development unit at the Joint University Libraries in Nashville, Tennessee, also received CLR assistance and carried out a number of needed projects during its seven-year existence. For these and ongoing management projects (including the Academic Library Management Intern Program described elsewhere in this report), CLR has allocated just over \$1.75 million since 1968, with an

22. Alphonse F. Trezza. "National Inventory of Library Needs, 1975." *Bowker Annual of Library and Book Trade Information* (New York and London, 1977), p. 247-52.

23. Association of Research Libraries. *ARL Statistics 1975-1976*. (Washington, 1976).

24. F. F. Clasquin and Jackson B. Cohen. "Prices of Physics and Chemistry Journals." *Science* 197 (1977):434.

25. Richard DeGennaro. "Austerity, Technology, and Resource-Sharing: Research Libraries Face the Future." *Library Journal* 100 (1975):922.

26. XX:47-51.

additional \$120,000 for smaller projects intended to deal with one aspect or another of library administration.

ARL's Office of University Library Management Studies

One of the principal benefits arising from the original management study, supported by the Council and performed with the advice of the American Council on Education and the Association of Research Libraries, was the 1970 establishment within ARL of the Office of University Library Management Studies (OMS).²⁷ In the past seven years OMS has proved to be a key element in the total effort to improve management and fiscal practices in libraries. The office director's participation in the Columbia University Libraries study provided much of the experience and background required for development of the Management Review and Analysis Program (MRAP), OMS's structured procedure for university library use in conducting an internal assessment of management practices, goals, and objectives. MRAP has been an important factor in helping libraries to free themselves of their often self-imposed limitations and to uncover and change operational patterns that are no longer relevant. To carry out the rigorous MRAP self-study a team is appointed that with the assistance of OMS personnel examines the library's decision-making process over a nine to twelve month period and recommends the organizational changes that are needed to improve day-to-day operations and to plan effectively for the future. Thus far 23 ARL university library members have completed their attempts to attain a more satisfactory management environment through MRAP. A nonmember, the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration Library, began the study process in September 1976.

Another major facet of the OMS program, information collection and dissemination, is designed to help libraries acquire the facts and theories that will stimulate improvement in research library operation and management. To this end OMS operates the Systems and Procedures Exchange Center (SPEC), a clearinghouse of information on current management practices of member libraries. Center staff survey ARL libraries on specific issues, analyze the documents the libraries are willing to share, issue *SPEC Flyers* that report the survey results, and select illustrative documents for inclusion in *SPEC Kits*. *SPEC Flyers* and *Kits* issued this past fiscal year dealt with the systems function in ARL libraries, use of support staff and student assistants, gift and exchange functions, preparation and presentation of the library budget, integration of nonprint media, and the determination of indirect cost rates.

A third aspect of OMS activity was strengthened this year by the addition of a training program coordinator whose assignments include developing and making available modules for in-house training programs in ARL libraries, coordinating training institutes, and overseeing

27. XX:48-49.

the office's training film program. OMS conducted its fourth Library Management Skills Institute in Kansas City, Missouri, in April 1977 and plans a fifth to take place in Columbia, Maryland, in November.

Since August 1970 when OMS was established, CLR has contributed just over half a million dollars for support of its activities. ARL itself and proceeds from the sale of the office's products and services have each year furnished an increasing amount to the OMS operation. In addition, OMS embarked this year on an extensive collection analysis project with the aid of a grant from the Andrew W. Mellon Foundation. The project will focus on the materials selection, acquisition, retention, and preservation policies of research libraries.

Measuring the Impact of MRAP

More than one fourth of the academic library members of the Association of Research Libraries have completed the Management Review and Analysis Program. Last year two Pennsylvania State University faculty members proposed that the Council support an attempt to evaluate the impact of the program on the individual participants.²⁸ Accordingly, Edward R. Johnson, associate librarian and assistant dean of libraries, and Stuart H. Mann, associate professor of operations research, began collecting data through questionnaires and personal interviews. In a presentation to the Research Roundtable of the American Library Association in June 1977 Johnson observed that evaluating MRAP has been extraordinarily difficult, in part because of the lack of an adequate evaluation technology, but also because of the broad scope of the program itself, its lengthy frame of operation, and the lack of a built-in evaluation structure. A final report on the CLR-funded study is expected shortly.

Academic Library Development Program

Large university and research libraries have not been the only institutions to suffer through difficulties caused by reduced budgets, staff turnover, university or library reorganization, and the introduction of automated procedures, all coupled with an increased demand for service. Small and mid-sized libraries have been similarly afflicted and have pressed for the kind of assistance that is available to larger libraries through OMS and MRAP. Thus the Council in 1975 initiated the Academic Library Development Program (ALDP) in the belief that smaller libraries too could benefit from looking closely at how they are meeting the needs of the campus community and finding ways to improve services to their users.²⁹

Phase one of the program was a pilot project at the University of North Carolina at Charlotte (UNCC) library where, under the direction of a

28. XX:49.

29. XIX:25-26; XX:50-51.

special project leader, staff developed a two-stage analytical process involving a study team and several task forces. The first stage entails an overview of the library's history, an environmental analysis, a goals assessment, and a needs survey. The second stage includes analyses of services, resources, management, and facilities. The UNCC project resulted in specific recommendations for improvements in the management of that library as well as a generalized manual for carrying out such a study at similar institutions.

In May 1976 the Council allocated funds for phase two of the program — testing and evaluating the procedure and manual developed in phase one in order to ensure that the model program would be of the greatest benefit to libraries. The first grants for this purpose went to the Carnegie-Mellon University and the University of Wisconsin—Parkside. As in the pilot project, the staffs of these libraries will be assisted by an advisory committee made up of representatives from the faculty, administration, and student body; librarians from other academic institutions; and representatives of appropriate professional associations. The CLR coordinator for the UNCC study will continue to act in that capacity during phase two. He and the OMS director, who has participated from the beginning in getting ALDP under way, will assist these and other institutions selected to take part in this phase of the work.

Improving Fiscal Practices

While most of the Council's programs have approached library management problems in a broad fashion, opportunities arise now and then to provide grants for projects that focus on particular aspects of administration. Such an award was made last year to Washington University in St. Louis, Missouri.³⁰ Using their own institution as a study site, library staff developed a generalized procedure for the internal financial auditing of university libraries. The final report, "Recommended Procedures for the Internal Financial Auditing of University Libraries," contains chapters on methodology, the relationship between auditor and university library administration, a questionnaire for evaluation of internal accounting control in a university library, auditing programs for original record examination and testing, and a discussion of auditing in computerized systems. Washington University has made the 96-page report widely available to ARL members and other university libraries. The study was planned by William H. Kurth, then university librarian, and carried forward on his untimely death by David S. Zubatsky, assistant university librarian.

Books for Building Planners

CLR support of field work connected with two publications that should be of assistance to library building planners came to an end during

30. XX:51.

the past year.³¹ William S. Pierce, chief of facilities planning at Pennsylvania State University, delivered the manuscript for his book "Planning the Library Interior" to its publisher, Marcel Dekker, Inc., in December 1976. The text is based on information gathered while Mr. Pierce was on sabbatical leave, when he visited over 230 institutions in 30 states and Canada. Ellsworth Mason, head of the Special Collections Department at the University of Colorado and a well-known library building consultant, also used a CLR grant to visit several institutions in order to include reviews of their buildings in his book, tentatively called "Mason on Library Buildings," to be published by Scarecrow Press.

31. XX:79.

Professional Development

MOST OF THE GRANTS MADE BY THE COUNCIL go to organizations and institutions for programs that have as their goal more efficient and economical library operation and thus improved services for library users. For the last eight years the Council has also made a significant number of awards to individuals in the belief that, given the opportunity to enhance their skills, practicing librarians will become more productive and better able to initiate needed improvements in library practices. The profession itself has also demonstrated its concern for upgrading the skills of librarians and library administrators. The varied programs currently offered under the rubric of continuing education by numerous institutions and organizations provide frequent opportunities for interaction among library theoreticians, administrators, and practitioners.

In the year covered by this report, CLR made awards to 25 librarians, selected on a competitive basis, to enable them to undertake self-developed fellowship studies, to enhance their credentials as scholars, and to gain firsthand knowledge of library management. Other active projects intended to contribute to the profession were a writing seminar and a survey of the compensation rates of academic librarians. A program that allowed selected Ph.D. holders to acquire degrees in librarianship has come to an end.

Academic Library Management Intern Program

In April 1977 the Council announced the names of the fourth class of CLR Management Interns.³² Each of the two women and three men will spend the 1977-78 academic year in close association with the director and top administrative staff of one of the nation's large academic research libraries, learning firsthand how they deal with day-to-day problems as well as with long-range goals. Interns also participate in special projects at their host institutions in order to increase their skills in such areas as budget preparation, staff development, and the like. As in past years, interns receive a stipend equal to their prior basic salary and benefits (up to \$20,000), some assistance in moving costs, and approved travel expenses.

The true measure of this program cannot be taken for several years. However, movement among the interns who have completed it indicates that the program's goal of developing a pool of librarians capable of assuming challenging positions in library management is a realistic one. Two former interns have become library directors; others have assumed responsible mid-level positions at Yale, Princeton, Columbia, and similar institutions. Several have elected to begin graduate studies leading to the Ph.D. in library science.

32. "Fourth Class of CLR Management Interns to Begin Work in Fall 1977." *CLR Recent Developments* 5 (May 1977):1-2.

Members of the 1977–78 class of management interns are listed below.

Graham R. Hill, collections librarian and director, Division of Archives and Special Collections, McMaster University, Hamilton, Ontario, is the first Canadian librarian to be selected for the program. Born in England, he received B.A. and M.A. degrees in English literature before emigrating to Canada. After receiving the M.L.S. from the University of Western Ontario in 1971 he joined the staff of McMaster. For his internship he has been assigned to work with W. Carl Jackson, dean of university libraries at Indiana University.

Jo Nell Hintner is head of the Cataloging Department of the Humanities Research Center (HRS), part of the library system at the University of Texas in Austin. After receiving an M.L.S. from that university in 1967, she joined its library staff and was promoted to her current position in 1974. She will spend her internship working with Richard M. Dougherty, university librarian at the University of California, Berkeley.

Shelley E. Phipps, orientation librarian at the University of Arizona, will intern with Connie Dunlap, library director at Duke University. Ms. Phipps received an M.L.S. from the University of Arizona in 1972. She served as head of Arizona's Pre-Catalog Section and as catalog librarian prior to being named to her present position.

Jordan M. Scepanski, assistant director of the library at the University of North Carolina, Charlotte, spent two years in the Peace Corps in Turkey before taking work leading to an M.L.S. at Emory University in 1967. His library career has included positions as an adult service librarian and as acting executive secretary of the Library Administration Division of the American Library Association. He assumed his present post in 1974. Frank P. Grisham, director of the Joint University Libraries in Nashville, Tennessee, will be his host during his internship year.

J. Daniel Vann, III, deputy chief librarian of the College of Staten Island, will move to California to intern with David C. Weber, director of the Stanford University Libraries. Dr. Vann received a Ph.D. in history at Yale (1965) followed by an M.L.S. at Emory University in 1971. His library career began at the Newberry Library, where he was a bibliographer and reference librarian. He served as library director at both Baptist College in Charleston (S.C.), and Keuka College (N.Y.) before going in 1971 to the College of Staten Island, an affiliate of the City University of New York.

Advanced Study Program for Librarians

Two years ago CLR offered an opportunity to librarians interested in enhancing their ability to work effectively with faculty, graduate students, and other scholars by increasing their own knowledge in a scholarly field. During the past year four outstanding librarians with demonstrated interest and competence in an area of the liberal arts and sciences were

chosen to pursue a year of full-time graduate study as the second class under the Council's Advanced Study Program for Librarians. The scholars receive stipends of up to \$15,000 based on prior salary and benefits. CLR also pays graduate school tuition and provides some assistance for appropriate moving costs. The 1977-78 class of advanced study scholars follow.

Joan M. Bechtel is assistant professor in the Department of Library Resources, Dickinson College. Ms. Bechtel plans to take courses at the University of Pennsylvania leading toward a master's degree in the intellectual history of the Renaissance and Reformation. She received a B.A. in history (1955) from Wilson College and an M.L.S. (1971) from Drexel University.

Jane A. Benson, reference librarian, Kent State University Libraries, and a graduate of Indiana University where she received both a B.A. in history and an M.L.S. (1966), will work toward a Ph.D. at the University of Michigan. Her field is modern American social history, particularly the history of women. Positions at Indiana University and Kent State have provided her with experience in documents, reference, interlibrary loan, and circulation.

George C. Hart is Latin American bibliographer, Ohio State University. Mr. Hart will begin a Ph.D. program at Indiana University where he will major in Spanish and Portuguese and minor in Latin American history. His academic credentials also were earned at Indiana; he received a B.A. in Spanish and Portuguese, an M.S. in Luzo-Brazilian literature, and an M.L.S. (1973). In addition to library experience in government publications, Latin American studies, reference, and cataloging, Mr. Hart spent two years as a Peace Corps volunteer in Brazil.

Beth J. Shapiro, urban affairs librarian, Michigan State University Libraries, will stay at Michigan State to continue work on a Ph.D. in urban sociology. She received both a B.S. and M.A. in sociology at that institution before moving to Western Michigan University, which awarded her an M.L.S. in 1974. She has been in her current position since 1972.

Fellowship Program

The professional development programs described above focus on quite specific needs in the library field. But the oldest and perhaps most far-reaching Council program in this area allows for candidate-initiated studies or projects. Since 1969, 199 librarians have been awarded CLR fellowships for self-developed programs intended to expand their outlook and knowledge as well as their usefulness to those they serve and to make a contribution to the profession itself. This past year 16 midcareer librarians were chosen to carry out programs that range from an examination of the collection development function in large research libraries to a

study of the use or nonuse of on-line bibliographic retrieval systems in science and technology libraries. Short-term internships may also receive awards under the terms of the fellowship program. A requirement of the program is that applicants be assured of at least a three-month leave of absence, preferably with salary, since the fellowship covers expenses only.

When the program began practically no librarians received paid leaves of absence for research and study as are usually provided for teaching faculty members. In fact, even unpaid leaves of absence were rare. An early goal of the Fellowship Program was to encourage employers to extend this privilege to librarians. It now appears that, whether as a result of the program or not, paid leaves of absence have increased; at the time of application all but five fellowship candidates for the 1977-78 program anticipated receiving such leaves.

The CLR Fellows for 1977-78 and their projects are listed below.

Walter C. Allen, associate professor, Graduate School of Library Science, University of Illinois, will study library building planning, including older buildings constructed in the modular fashion to determine what advantage library managers have taken of this flexibility.

Wilmer H. Baatz, assistant director, Indiana University Libraries, will examine the collection development function in large research libraries in the United States.

Elsie Lilius Bell, chief of main library, Oklahoma County Libraries System, will explore current priorities of selected main public libraries in standard metropolitan statistical areas, with an emphasis on the financial and functional relationships between main and branch libraries.

Carolyn P. Brown, chief, information services, National Bureau of Standards, will study use and nonuse of on-line bibliographic retrieval systems in science and technology libraries.

Lois Mai Chan, associate professor, College of Library Science, University of Kentucky, will develop a treatise on the *Library of Congress Subject Headings* that will include a theoretical consideration of its basic principles and its application by the Library of Congress.

Josephine Riss Fang, professor, School of Library Science, Simmons College, plans to study the informative and educational functions of libraries in contemporary China and their impact on the socio-economic and cultural aspects of Chinese society.

Robert W. Karrow, Jr., curator of maps, Newberry Library, will compile a comprehensive annotated bibliography of local and regional cartobibliographies of the United States and Canada before 1900.

Mark Kovacic, gifts and exchange librarian, Pennsylvania State University Libraries, will study the organization and function of gift and exchange programs in academic libraries.

Frederick C. Lynden, assistant chief, acquisitions department, Stanford University Libraries, will examine aspects of library materials budgets at selected privately supported university libraries.

Kathryn J. Owens, catalog librarian, Indiana State University Library, will add to her knowledge of music librarianship through an internship at the Sibley Music Library of the Eastman School of Music.

Alvis H. Price, associate personnel officer, University of California at Los Angeles Library, will investigate staff training programs in selected large research libraries in order to develop a model system.

Phyllis A. Richmond, professor, School of Library Science, Case Western Reserve University, will prepare an introductory text to PRECIS (Preserved Context Index System) for North American users.

Anne Roberts, associate librarian, State University of New York (SUNY) at Albany, will study credit courses in library instruction taught by librarians in the SUNY university centers and four-year colleges.

Shiro Saito, associate university librarian for public services, University of Hawaii Library, will prepare a comprehensive research guide to Philippine social science information sources.

Margaret F. Steig, assistant professor, School of Library Service, Columbia University, will study the origins and development of periodicals in the field of history.

Sheh Wong, head, East Asian Library, University of Minnesota, will augment his knowledge and training in *Pan pen hsüeh*, a traditional Chinese study of rare books or old editions.

Library Training for Ph.D. Holders

The Council often encourages and supports a variety of approaches to the solution of a particular library problem. The Advanced Study Program was developed as one way of addressing the need of research and academic libraries for librarians with advanced skills in traditional fields of scholarship. Another approach grew out of the realization that librarianship had benefited enormously from the efforts of distinguished librarians who had entered the field after experience in scholarship and teaching. The Council in 1974 funded an experimental program at the University of Chicago Graduate Library School to encourage suitable scholars to adopt this route.³³ Following a nationwide competition that

33. XX:69.

attracted over 100 candidates, fellowships for work leading to a master's degree in librarianship were offered to nine talented scholars, who had already earned Ph.D.s in other fields. According to the final report, three of the scholars have become bibliographers (two with related teaching responsibilities), two have moved into library management, and one is an archivist. Of the other three, one has returned to teaching, one is teaching in an information-related field while looking for a suitable library position, and one, a recent mother unable to relocate, is unemployed.

In an assessment of the program, the Chicago library school dean last year commented that having a Ph.D. was not necessarily an advantage in the tight library job market if candidates had no previous work experience in libraries. For lower positions the applicant may be regarded as over-qualified, while for higher positions the lack of experience is an inhibiting factor. Sometimes candidates were viewed with a certain suspicion as to their reasons for wanting to shift from teaching and research to librarianship. Regardless of academic qualifications, lack of experience coupled at times with lack of personal mobility appeared to be the greatest obstacle to a successful job hunt.

ALA Concludes Salary Survey

The recruitment of talented, well-qualified individuals to the library profession has been hampered over many years by a troublesome problem—poor compensation. In an attempt to document an answer to the question of whether the profession pays enough to attract highly competent young people and thereafter keep them in its ranks, the Council has supported a series of salary surveys of college and university librarians.³⁴ The fourth survey, this time conducted by the Association of College and Research Libraries and based on 1975-76 figures, was published in October 1976. The conclusions were not optimistic. The unattractive salaries for academic librarians reported in earlier surveys not only continue but the problem has been aggravated as a result of inflation and other economic pressures. In addition, the pyramidal staffing structure of libraries remains substantially the same.

As in the past an attempt was made to parallel the faculty compensation survey conducted by the American Association of University Professors. In this regard, the 1975-76 salaries of academic librarians compare generally with those of assistant professors. Since the survey contained comparative figures on men and women librarians as well as minorities, it should provide a solid base of data for planners concerned with equal opportunity for academic librarians.

Writing Seminar for New England Librarians

In the belief that a real need exists for an improvement in the quality of professional writing in the field of librarianship, the University of Con-

34. XX:63-64.

necticut in August 1976 successfully sought Council funds for the New England Academic Librarians' Writing Seminar. According to seminar director Norman D. Stevens, the program treats writing as "a planned and organized activity" with opportunities provided for the ten participants to exchange ideas and to review and criticize each other's work. Six meetings of the group have been held to date. Eleven articles have been submitted for publication; one has already appeared³⁵ and two others have thus far been accepted. Another expected product of the seminar is a book of essays to be published by Scarecrow Press.

35. Norman D. Stevens. "A Dutch Museum Acts as Keeper of the Library Past." *Wilson Library Bulletin* 52 (1977):841-43.

Libraries and Their Users

BUSY MODERN LIBRARIES bear little resemblance to the repositories of ancient times whose primary purpose was to safeguard precious manuscripts and books that were available to only a few of the elect. Today's libraries are public service institutions with an obligation to provide their multitudes of users with access to information in a variety of forms. In recent years interest in the library's potential as an active element in education has caused a reevaluation of what providing access to information means. Traditional concepts of service have come under critical review and new patterns are developing in all types of libraries.

The goal of all Council programs has been to improve the efficiency of library operations so that users will be better served. Since the late 1960s CLR has initiated several programs intended to achieve that goal by focusing specifically on relationships between libraries and users. The programs aim at assisting libraries of all kinds. For example, in May of this year CLR supported the Fourth Assembly of State Librarians, who met at the Library of Congress to explore with LC staff more effective methods of cooperation and mutual assistance. However, since the Council's special clientele has always been academic and research libraries, most of its activities in this area as in others have been devoted to their particular needs.

ACADEMIC LIBRARY SERVICES

With the exception of public libraries, libraries usually exist to serve a specific sector of the population. On a university or college campus the library's clientele is primarily the academic community — students, faculty, and administrators. Student activism in the late 1960s and early 1970s created an upheaval that led to a reconsideration of many concepts in higher education, some of which concerned the relationship of the academic library to the educational process. According to one observer, activism manifested itself among the rank and file of the academic librarians not only in a more vocal drive for faculty status but also in a call for a more aggressive service policy and greater visibility. It was clear that many undergraduates no longer entered college equipped with basic library skills and often graduated no wiser in this regard, never acquiring the familiarity with library resources and effective access that could serve them throughout their lives. In an effort to change the situation some librarians began to seek formal and informal means of teaching library resources and methods, a process generally known as bibliographic instruction. However, they found little in the literature that could help them in the way of reports of successful programs of this kind or guides to useful information. Working through the American Library Association, a group of concerned librarians began in the late 1960s to develop professional structures (e.g., committees, task forces, etc.) that would allow for communication and an interchange of experience.

The College Library Program

About the same time that librarians began seriously to develop professional mechanisms for exploring problems associated with bibliographic instruction, the Council launched its own search for an effective way to deal with the matter. That search began with a question: how can academic libraries be encouraged to assume a more active, meaningful role in undergraduate education? CLR concluded that a program was needed to stimulate administrators and teaching faculty members as well as librarians to take a fresh look at how the library should function in the academic community. In 1969 the Council initiated the College Library Program and with the National Endowment for the Humanities established a fund from which matching grants could be made to selected four-year accredited colleges and universities. The grants, made in response to carefully developed proposals, are intended to encourage a broad range of activities that will provide cohesive links between library services and classroom instruction and thereby strengthen the library's role in the teaching-learning process. Each institution is required to allocate funds over and beyond the regular library budget to share the cost of the total program.

Four grants in the past fiscal year bring to 27 the number of institutions that have received College Library Program awards. The new recipients and brief overviews of their projected programs are listed below.

Johnson C. Smith University in Charlotte, North Carolina, will make basic changes and improvements in its library program so that the library can become "fundamentally a teaching facility of the institution." A staff member trained in reference work and familiar with the university's curriculum will serve as orientation librarian, working chiefly with the English and history department faculty to improve library services to students. It is estimated that nearly three fourths of the student body will have the opportunity to improve their library skills by the end of the program.

The University of Evansville in Indiana has planned a Library-Humanities Program that will involve undergraduates in bibliographic instruction throughout their college careers. After receiving basic orientation and library skills instruction in freshman composition courses, students will encounter more specialized research tools and strategies in upper division humanities courses. Qualified undergraduates will then move into independent study and research under the joint direction of a faculty member and a librarian. Finally, selected undergraduates will serve as student interns to help other students engaged in the program's initial stages.

Northwestern University in Evanston, Illinois, will carry out its Scholar Librarian Program with the help of three subject specialist librarians with Ph.D.s in humanistic disciplines. The specialists will engage in such instructional activities as teaching formal courses in library-related areas,

supervising student research, developing humanities collections for reference and instructional use, and lecturing on the bibliography of their areas of special knowledge.

St. Olaf College in Northfield, Minnesota, will pursue its Course-Related Library Instruction Program in two phases. First, humanities faculty will pinpoint the bibliographic knowledge and library skills that their majors should acquire. Following this, librarians, with the aid of senior student associates, will give bibliographic assistance in developing course components that will provide these skills and will guide students in their use of the library to fulfill course requirements.

The guidelines governing the College Library Program have changed recently as a result of a rather complete evaluation by a committee of librarians appointed by NEH and CLR.³⁶ The program is now more competitive than in the past, with applications accepted twice yearly—in the spring and in the fall. Proposals may be made for programs that range from three to five years. Participating institutions must contribute at least 25 percent of the total program budget from funds not already allocated to the library. As in past years, grants may be requested only for programs that deal with the humanities and those social sciences that share the concerns and employ the methods of the humanities.

Project LOEX

One of the earliest College Library Program awards went to Eastern Michigan University. Although the grant period ended in 1975, that program has had far-reaching effects, for out of it came two activities that are still continuing full strength. One, a conference on orientation and instruction with an annual attendance of about 150 academic librarians, was held for the seventh time this spring. The other is Project LOEX (Library Orientation-instruction Exchange). Established in 1972, Project LOEX is an international clearinghouse for materials and information concerning library instruction and orientation.³⁷ A 1975 Council grant supports LOEX activities through December 1977. According to recent reports, the clearinghouse continues to enjoy a constant growth in membership and has been able to keep pace with an increasing number of requests for reports of developments in the field. As of June 1977, 679 libraries had become LOEX members and had contributed 8,808 items, such as workbooks, video tapes, bibliographies, course syllabi, etc., to the project's circulating collection. LOEX staff prepare traveling exhibits of instructional materials (which were used in 15 professional conferences in 1976), report on developments in the field, assist individual librarians with their personal research, and prepare tailored lists of materials available on computer-assisted library instruction, faculty library guides and handbooks, library instruction services to the visually impaired, and others.

36. XX:53-54.

37. XX:55.

This past year CLR made a second award to Project LOEX to fund its activities to June 30, 1978, when Eastern Michigan University will assume full support responsibility.

Library Service Enhancement Program

There is, of course, more than one route to successful integration of library services with academic teaching programs and increased library use. The College Library Program was the Council's first major effort to accomplish the purpose. In 1975 the problem was addressed from a slightly different vantage point when CLR initiated the Library Service Enhancement Program.³⁸ Under the program, now in its second year, library directors designate a project librarian who explores with faculty, students, and administrators potential activities that will expand the library's role in the academic life of the college or university in the sciences as well as in the humanities. The Council grant in each case provides an amount not to exceed the salary and benefits of the designated project librarian who is relieved of normal duties for the academic year in order to spend full time on the project. Each institution is required to appoint for the grant period a beginning professional librarian; the balance of the funds is for approved project-related expenses.

This year 13 institutions were selected from a field of 86 applicants for programs to take place during the 1977-78 academic year. They are Beloit College (Wisconsin), Colorado College, Georgia Southern College, Georgia State University, Glenville State College (West Virginia), Guilford College (North Carolina), Hampton Institute (Virginia), Joint University Libraries (Tennessee), Lake Forest College (Illinois), Tusculum College (Tennessee), University of Colorado at Colorado Springs, University of Missouri at Kansas City, and Wayne State University (Michigan). Each program was developed in the context of the individual institution's needs. Several call for developing research components as part of established courses; others plan such activities as workshops or seminars for faculty or experimentation with the potential of audiovisual techniques in library orientation and instruction. One library is entering into a full-scale curriculum development program with the science faculty.

In order to ensure that applicants would be competing with peer institutions, the proposals for the 1977-78 academic year were divided into groups based on the classification established by the Carnegie Commission on Higher Education in *A Classification of Institutions of Higher Education* (Berkeley, California, 1973).

Aids for Scholarship

To be of the most help to scholars and other researchers, libraries must be able to provide ready bibliographic access to materials that may exist in a variety of formats. They can do this only through a host of specialized

38. XX:55-56.

publications and computerized data bases that describe what has been published in certain fields and often where it can be located and who can use it. Over the years, the Council has supported the preparation of several guides to resources as a way of assisting libraries to provide better service for their clientele.

The Council's participation in two such endeavors was completed during the past fiscal year. A survey of Arabic, Persian, and Turkish manuscripts in the United States, prepared with the assistance of a CLR grant under the auspices of the American Council of Learned Societies, will be published by G. K. Hall and Company.³⁹ Another CLR grant supported research carried out in England by Frank Rodgers, director of the Portland State University library, preparatory to his writing a manual of British government publications.⁴⁰

In a new action this year, the Council provided a small award to J. Periam Danton, professor in the School of Library and Information Studies, University of California—Berkeley, to enable him to complete a 1966–75 supplement to the *Index to Festschriften in Librarianship* that will be published by Verlag Dokumentation in Munich. The Council had also supported the original volume, which was published by R. R. Bowker in 1970.⁴¹ As an additional service to librarians and scholars, CLR continues to fund the preparation of a regular column in *Choice* magazine that contains evaluations of new magazines and journals within a short time of their appearance.⁴² Published by the American Library Association, *Choice* is a book-selection guide primarily for college and university libraries and was undertaken with Council support. CLR also assists the annual compilation of law library statistics that appears as a regular feature in the May issue of *Law Library Journal*.⁴³

THE PUBLIC LIBRARY

Improved services in academic libraries are a boon to those who are able to pursue customary paths to higher education. There are, however, many adults who wish to obtain academic credit or need guidance in learning for vocational or avocational pursuits and who for a variety of reasons cannot take advantage of the usual academic route. Growing numbers of individuals in this situation are turning for help to public libraries where they are discovering programs especially adapted to the needs of the adult independent learner. Educators and librarians are working more closely than ever before in the Open University, the College Level Examination Program (CLEP), course-by-newspaper offerings, ex-

39. XX:57.

40. *Ibid.*

41. XI:18; XIV:40.

42. XIX:33.

43. XX:78.

ternal degree, and similar programs. Governments, educational organizations, and international agencies have started programs for "lifetime learning" and "individualized study." To call attention to the expanded role that public libraries can play in these new efforts, in 1973 the Commission on Non-Traditional Study, composed of outstanding U. S. educators, described the public library as "literally a college around the corner. . . the primary community resource for individual intellectual growth." But, the commission ruefully acknowledged, "their vast capabilities have often been ignored."⁴⁴ Several Council-supported programs have attempted to correct this situation.

Library Services for Independent Study

The Council's involvement in independent learning activities began in 1968 when CLR acted to bring together educators, planners, and public library leaders. Then, with the College Entrance Examination Board (CEEB) and NEH, from 1971 to 1973 the Council supported an experimental program at the Dallas Public Library to demonstrate the role an American public library might play in assisting independent learners.⁴⁵ A principal goal of the project was to determine whether public libraries could feasibly provide materials and counseling for adults who wished to study for academic credit but were unable or unwilling to attend the regular class sessions offered by neighboring institutions of higher education. In addition to demonstrating that public libraries can make an important contribution in independent learning, the project experience pointed up the need for a central coordinating body to serve as a source of communication and information for libraries desiring to establish this new service.

Thus in 1972 the Council joined with the College Entrance Examination Board, NEH, and the U. S. Office of Education to establish at CEEB the Office of Library Independent Study and Guidance Projects.⁴⁶ For several years the office provided leadership in an extensive program of training, resource planning, and experimental studies geared toward helping public libraries become effective community learning centers. Nine public libraries cooperated with the office to develop a coordinated program known as the Learner's Advisory Service, which could be used by any adult interested in embarking on a serious, sustained effort to learn, independent of a formal institution. No restrictions were placed on the goals of the learner or on the content of the program. Thus the adult learner could be working toward academic credit through CLEP, toward job improvement or the acquisition of a new skill, or toward gaining knowledge for personal enjoyment. In 1976, as the end of the grant period approached, the office organized a nationwide series of seminars to provide information on the benefits, ramifications, and pitfalls of the new service and to encourage other public libraries to adopt it.

44. Commission on Non-Traditional Study. *Diversity By Design* (San Francisco, 1973), p. 83.

45. XX:59-60

46. XX:60-61.

Consortium for Public Library Innovation

To carry on the task of developing learner's advisory services as well as to engage in further experimentation, research, and evaluation of other useful and innovative public library services, a Consortium for Public Library Innovation was formed in 1976. Comprising the original nine public libraries — Atlanta, Baltimore, Denver, Miami, Portland (Maine), Salt Lake City, St. Louis, Tulsa, and Woodbridge (New Jersey)—plus the Minneapolis Public Library, the consortium has continued data collection and reporting for member libraries on their adult independent study and guidance projects. Promotion of program planning and evaluation techniques, provision of staff development opportunities, and dissemination of research findings to policy makers and others in the library profession and government are also objectives of the new group. A Council grant, awarded in August 1976, is assisting the research activities of the consortium.

Other Public Library Activities

Two other Council-supported programs involving public libraries were active in the past fiscal year. In November 1976 CLR awarded \$10,000 to the New York Public Library to support research efforts of the "National Citizens Emergency Committee to Save Our Public Libraries." Dissemination of the research findings is intended to inform community agencies, particularly the media and citizen organizations, of the need for federal and state action to implement a public library funding program. During the year the committee issued several "Fact Sheets on Library Users." Topics included "Public Libraries and the Poor—Helping the Disadvantaged Help Themselves" and "Public Libraries and Education—Serving Student Needs Is Still the Public Library's Number One Job."

The second award went to the Public Library Association in 1974 to enable it to commission such prominent individuals as George Plimpton, Herman Badillo, and Norman Cousins to prepare chapters of a publication that would be an "eloquent statement to direct widespread attention to the American public library as an active community agent capable of meeting the real needs of real people today and in the future."⁴⁷ The book, to be entitled "The Library Connection," will be published by the American Library Association early in the fall of 1977.

47. XX:59.

Preservation and Micrographics

IN 1974 UNESCO ESTIMATED that 580,000 distinct titles had been published worldwide that year.⁴⁸ According to tests run on the types of papers frequently used in their production, if left untreated most of the books will be unusable in 2074. Yet if society is to make continued progress the knowledge contained in these books must be preserved. Herein lies a problem of mammoth proportions. Although methods of restoration are available, most are very expensive.

The problem of paper deterioration is not a new one. It was recognized as critical when the Council was established, and programs to deal with it were among the first to be funded. This year was the last for one of those programs, the operation of the W. J. Barrow Research Laboratory. The Council's board regretfully concluded that, in view of the Council's many obligations to libraries and its own funding situation, and because of the increasing costs of the independent laboratory, it could no longer be supported.

W. J. Barrow Research Laboratory

Thus at the conclusion of the fiscal year covered by this report, the activities of one of CLR's oldest and best known undertakings came to an end. Support of the Barrow Laboratory — which has amounted to well over \$1 million — began 20 years ago with the funding of William J. Barrow's seminal investigation into the quality of papers normally used in book manufacture.⁴⁹ His study confirmed what had already been suspected — the quality of book stock left much to be desired. With the Council's help Barrow set up a laboratory where he determined that modern methods of manufacture produced paper with a high acid content, a principal reason for its deterioration. His next step was to generate specifications for a paper both physically durable and chemically stable for hundreds of years of normal use. Such papers are now commercially available but are, sad to say, little used by book publishers. In contrast, library cards printed on permanent and durable stock, an outgrowth of Barrow's paper specifications, are now common in libraries.

Barrow died in 1967, but the work he began went on under other leadership. This past year was marked by large-scale field testing of a machine and process capable of safely and quickly deacidifying fifty to one hundred books at a time. The process, morpholine vapor-phase deacidification, took almost ten years to develop, refine, and test. Testing is now complete, and licensing of the process is in the hands of the Research Corporation, a nonprofit organization that includes patent development among its concerns. Any return from the venture will be used to support further research. Much of the specialized equipment that CLR

48. Chandler B. Grannis. "International Book Trade Statistics: Imports, Exports, Title Output, Translations." *Bowker Annual of Library & Book Trade Information* (New York and London, 1977), p. 451.

49. I:21-22 and subsequent annual reports.

purchased for the Barrow Laboratory over the years has been placed on indefinite loan at the Carnegie-Mellon Institute of Research, Carnegie-Mellon University, for its forthcoming program in paper preservation. A collection of very old books used by Barrow in his early studies has been given to the Library of Congress.

National Preservation Program

The Council's interest in fostering wider use of existing conservation techniques was highlighted in December 1976 by its support of a library of Congress planning conference for a national preservation program. The several experts who spoke at the meeting generally concurred with a background paper prepared by the LC Preservation Office calling for

- A large-scale microfilming project to preserve the intellectual content of deteriorating materials that do not warrant the greater expense of physical preservation. This project is seen as incorporating: (a) surveys of holdings most urgently requiring microfilming, (b) development of bibliographic and technical standards for microforms, (c) establishment of a dedicated filming center, and (d) creation of a procedure under which selected research libraries would contribute master microfilm negatives for a national collection.
- A program of preservation and restoration for those library materials that are valuable beyond the information they contain. This part of the national program would include training programs for conservators, workshops in conservation, preparation of training aids, development of emergency salvage teams, and creation of regional conservation centers.
- Actions to ensure preservation of future library materials to include a preservation collection, perhaps with the help of an amendment to the copyright law that would require a third deposit copy for the purpose. This part of the program also calls for low temperature storage facilities and appropriate record keeping and information dissemination systems for the collection.

Summing up the two days of deliberation, Warren J. Haas, CLR vice president, called for creation of a small action-oriented committee to guide a coordinated national preservation and conservation program of the general kind described above. Such a group, the Ad Hoc Advisory Committee for a National Preservation Program, has been formed and has held its first meeting. A senior CLR staff member serves on the committee, whose meetings are supported by a CLR grant. The Library of Congress has appointed a National Preservation Program Officer to organize, develop, and manage the national program.

Conservation of Photographs

Certain categories of library material require specialized care, i.e., collections of photographs. Yet many libraries, museums, historical societies, and other institutions have important historical photograph collections and no staff knowledgeable in conservation techniques to handle them. To aid such institutions and other collectors, the American Association for State and Local History published this year the CLR-supported *Collection, Use and Care of Historical Photographs* by Robert A. Weinstein and Larry Booth.⁵⁰ A handsome, lavishly illustrated volume, the work answers such questions as these: Can you clean a daguerreotype — or distinguish it from a tintype? Can you prevent flaking of collodion plates? How do you index a photographic collection? Legal questions, making a collection available for reproduction or research, archival storage, cataloging — these and other topics are covered by the authors in a concise, readable style that should ensure the book's continuing usefulness.

Micrographics

Microforms now compose a significant portion of academic and research library collections. Often they are purchased or produced to replace items that have deteriorated or, like newspapers, will deteriorate rapidly. In some cases they are acquired as the only format in which newly published items appear. Microform holdings of ARL member libraries expanded 15.5 percent between 1974 and 1975 and another 9.1 percent the following year. The Library of Congress counts over 800,000 reels of microfilm and well over a million microfiche in its collection. College, junior college, and university libraries annually add microforms worth over \$7 million to their holdings. Yet there continue to be a number of constraints on their use. These include the limitations of reading equipment, insufficient bibliographic aids, lack of standardization, and negative attitudes toward the medium on the part of many librarians and users.

Since its inception CLR has sought ways to deal with these and other barriers to full utilization of microforms. On a continuing basis a CLR staff member dedicates a significant portion of his time to efforts to ameliorate the problems associated with microforms. In addition to managing the Council's projects in this area, he regularly participates in seminars and other educational programs, provides informal question-answering and consulting services to libraries, and works with organizations such as the National Micrographics Association and appropriate groups within the American Library Association.

50. XVI:32; XX:78.

Computer Output Microfilm

A development in the field of micrographics that is rapidly gaining ground is the use of computer output microfilm (COM) in mechanized information processing systems. Already a number of library systems are replacing or supplementing their card catalogs with COM versions. The Library of Congress is experimenting with COM editions of the *Library of Congress Subject Headings* and the *Register of Additional Locations (RAL)*, a supplement to the *National Union Catalog* that carries additional locations for titles published from 1956 to the present. A CLR grant supports RAL-related studies concerning expansion of its data base and a user-oriented format and publication schedule.⁵¹

In line with these developments the Council in 1976 began an investigation into the potential of COM for libraries, with emphasis on bibliographic applications.⁵² The study has taken longer than originally anticipated but it is now proceeding well and should be concluded in the near future. At that time a decision will be made as to whether additional studies are needed.

Princeton's Microform Program

Princeton University has made an exceptional commitment to upgrading all aspects of utilization of its microform holdings. With budgeted funds and grants from a number of sources, the Princeton Library has

- Moved the microtext reading room to a renovated and more accessible location on the main floor of the Firestone Library.
- Undertaken a major program to improve bibliographic access.
- Installed a large number of new microform reading machines.

To ensure that these important improvements are effectively utilized, the Council made a grant of \$10,000 to Princeton for expenses associated with training and orientation of the library's staff and its users.⁵³ The award supports educational travel for the newly appointed microform librarian, individualized in-house training of staff of the Microforms Division, a day-long seminar for non-Microforms Division staff, and orientation sessions for faculty and students. In addition, the CLR grant is being used to produce special graphics for the microtext room and machines, to investigate the effectiveness of the new facilities and services, and to publish a report on the project.

51. XX:44.

52. XX:42-43.

53. "Princeton University to Improve Microform Service." *CLR Recent Developments* 4 (December 1976):4.

Microform Collections Guide

During the year Suzanne Dodson, head of the Government Documents and Microforms Division of the library at the University of British Columbia, used a CLR grant to complete her manuscript of a guide to large collections in microform.⁵⁴ It is expected that the work will appear in print in the next few months and that it will become a vital element in intellectual access to a sizeable group of micropublications.

54. XX:45.

International Library Cooperation

THE COUNCIL'S CONCERN with the problems facing libraries has not been restricted to those that affect American libraries only. CLR adopted an international view at its inception and has continued to encourage programs designed to foster cooperation and the exchange of information among the world's libraries and archives. Nowhere is the need for cooperation more evident than in automation and bibliographic control. Indeed, the logical extension of national library and information service networks is an international library system made up of national and multinational networks. Such a system would undoubtedly use a variety of computerized and manual techniques to exchange bibliographic information about the world's publications, a number estimated by UNESCO statisticians at well over half a million new titles each year. To gain bibliographic control over this quantity of material on an international basis requires the same careful planning and the same development and acceptance of standards that must take place in a national program. Several developments of recent years, including the work on the revision of the *Anglo-American Cataloging Rules* described earlier, have led the world's librarians to believe that an international library system may be within reach at last.

International Federation of Library Associations and Institutions

Since 1971 much of the Council's support of international library cooperation has been channeled through the International Federation of Library Associations and Institutions (IFLA), an organization in which many countries, including the United States, participate on an equal basis. Three CLR grants, awarded in 1970, 1973, and 1976 and totalling \$364,000, have enabled IFLA to strengthen its administrative and staff operations in order to assure its effectiveness.⁵⁵

Chief among the secretariat's recent activities has been the reorganization of the federation that was approved in August 1976, at IFLA's 42nd General Council Meeting in Lausanne, Switzerland. Under the new constitution IFLA's professional role is broadened "to promote international understanding, cooperation, discussion, research and development in all fields of library activity, including bibliography, information sciences, and the education of personnel, and to provide a body through which librarianship can be presented in matters of international interest."⁵⁶ Categories of membership were also expanded so that such institutions as individual libraries and library schools could have voting privileges, hence the recent change in the federation's name, if not its acronym.⁵⁷

55. XX:71-72.

56. Margreet Wijnstroom. "The New Constitution of IFLA." *Bowker Annual of Library & Book Trade Information* (New York and London, 1977), p. 409.

57. IFLA added "and Institutions" to its name in 1976 but decided to retain the four-letter acronym.

The most recent CLR grant for the secretariat, awarded in 1976, was for the purpose of enabling IFLA to implement its new professional program. Thus far 24 sections have been established, grouped together in seven divisions by type of library or library activity (e.g., general research libraries, special libraries, collections and services, management and technology, etc.); an eighth division, the key to the federation's new regional development program, will provide an effective basis for participation in the organization by the library profession of the Third World countries of Asia, Africa, and Latin America. IFLA's leaders hope that the federation can now provide better leadership and resources in helping these countries solve some of their library and literacy problems through mutual assistance and cooperation.

IFLA International Office for Universal Bibliographic Control

IFLA's new constitution notes that the organization intends to cooperate with other international associations in the information field and will set up offices to carry out specific tasks. One such office, the International Office for Universal Bibliographic Control, was established in 1974 as an extension of the CLR-supported IFLA Cataloguing Secretariat, which was given the added responsibility of assisting in the development of a system of international bibliographic communication generally known as universal bibliographic control (UBC). A successful system for universal bibliographic control requires that each nation assume the responsibility for preparing and making available bibliographic records of its own publications, both print and nonprint; utilization of accepted standards will ensure that the records can be readily employed in both manual and machine-readable systems anywhere in the world.

The major thrust of the UBC office has been to promote and assist projects that will aid the international standardization of bibliographic records and to support national plans for improving bibliographic control. In addition to contributions from national libraries and other international library and bibliographic organizations, the office has received three awards from the Council.⁵⁸ The third grant, covering the period from July 1, 1977, to June 30, 1981, was made this past year, bringing the total CLR allocation to the office to \$364,200.

UBC office functions to date have centered on the provision of services to working groups and individuals engaged in special bibliographic projects, the collection and dissemination of information relating to bibliographic standardization, liaison and coordination among national and international cataloging and bibliographic organizations, and editorial and publishing activities. The performance of these functions has led to a new role for the office, that of an international bibliographic center. This is reflected in various projects the office staff has undertaken recently, such as planning the program content and helping conduct the 1976 IFLA World-Wide Seminar in Seoul, Korea, and organizing, planning, and

58. XX:72-74.

preparing background documents for the September 1977 UNESCO-sponsored International Congress on National Bibliographies.

IFLA foresees that its UBC Office may become even more significant as a center for activities that will further develop and maintain a system of universal bibliographic control. These activities might include acting as secretariat for IFLA's new subject-oriented round tables that are directly involved in the maintenance of UBC (e.g., cataloging-in-publication), or perhaps assisting expert monitoring panels to watch over the development and extension of existing manuals and bibliographic tools like the various International Standard Bibliographic Descriptions (ISBD) and the recently published Universal MARC (UNIMARC) format.

International MARC Network Study

The key role played by the IFLA International Office for Universal Bibliographic Control is illustrated by its involvement in an international bibliographic network study proposed by a group of national librarians who met in Paris in October 1975. A CLR grant enabled the Library of Congress to join with the national libraries of Australia, Canada, France, and Great Britain in funding the study.⁵⁹ The UBC Office has acted as treasurer for the study's steering committee, drawing up contracts, paying fees, and providing statements of accounts. The office has also prepared the portion of the study that deals with incompatibilities among bibliographic records of various nations and plans to publish it as a separate document.

International Council on Archives

In 1975 CLR awarded funds to strengthen the secretariat of another important international organization, the International Council on Archives (ICA).⁶⁰ Now concluding the second year of the three-year grant that enabled it to acquire an executive assistant and a secretary, ICA has engaged in a broad span of activities designed to foster the development of archives throughout the world. Recently the secretariat signed contracts with UNESCO for seven projects. These include the preparation of guides to the archives of the United Nations and to the sources of the history of Asia, Oceania, and North Africa; development of a statistical model for archival systems; and a study on establishing in developing areas regional centers for restoration and reprography. ICA is also supported by dues from member archives, by income received from contracts and the sale of publications, and by the allotment of space within the French National Archives.

A related grant was made early in the fiscal year to the National Archives and Records Service (NARS) to support meetings of the ICA Committee on Archival Development and its regional rapporteurs. The

59. XX:74.

60. XIX:38; XX:74.

meetings took place in Washington in conjunction with the 1976 NARS-hosted International Archives Congress and were considered to be successful in advancing work toward the establishment of a survey of Third World archival development needs and in completing the structure of ICA's International Archival Development Fund.

Cooperative Efforts in Latin America

For several years the Organization of American States (OAS) has been engaged in laying the foundation for an inter-American automated bibliographic network. The Council assisted this effort in 1973 by providing support for a meeting in Colombia, during which the participants discussed items concerned with centralized cataloging and the use of MARCAL (Manual de catalogación mecanizada para América Latina). In October 1976 CLR supported another meeting, this one in Mexico, following a conference of the Federation Internationale de Documentation (FID). At this meeting the MARCAL manual was approved with some revisions, along with the OAS plans for developing an inter-American network for the transmission of bibliographic information. This step has made it possible for work to proceed on the formulation of networks in the Caribbean and on the extension of the bibliographic services offered by the southwestern AMIGOS Bibliographic Council to the Caribbean, Central America, and Colombia.

Cooperation through International Exchange

Although most of the assistance provided by CLR in the area of international cooperation is channeled through the work of such organizations as IFLA or ICA, progress also depends on the efforts of individuals. Because many of the problems affecting libraries transcend national boundaries, a multinational exchange of ideas must occur before mutually beneficial solutions can be attained. Accordingly, the Council has from time to time found it possible to defray travel costs incurred by U. S. librarians who have leadership responsibilities in international gatherings. Prior to making grants of this nature CLR draws heavily on the advice and knowledge of outside consultants to ensure that the Council's support will have a significant impact in promoting international cooperation in librarianship. Thus a CLR grant permits the participation of the president of the Seminar on the Acquisition of Latin American Library Materials in the Brazilian Library and Documentation Congress to be held in Pôrto Alegre July 3-9, 1977. Council support also enabled the chairperson of the Library Materials Price Index Committee of ALA's Resources and Technical Services Division to attend a workshop on European book prices and production held in the Netherlands in April 1977. Two other American librarians received CLR assistance that allowed them to contribute important information on the American experience in network

development to a British conference on the topic sponsored by the SCONUL (Standing Conference on National and University Libraries) and the Library Association.

In a similar effort to extend understanding of library programs and methods beyond national boundaries, the Council occasionally is able to provide influential foreign librarians with opportunities to study developments outside their own countries. This year the deputy chief librarian of the Royal Library in the Netherlands made a study tour of library buildings, networks, and automation projects in the United States with the help of a Council grant.

Publications Resulting from CLR-Supported Programs and Fellowships 1976-1977*

Part 1: Programs

The Growth of a National Library System

Library of Congress Network Advisory Group. *Toward a National Library and Information Service Network: The Library Bibliographic Component*, preliminary ed. Washington, D.C.: Library of Congress, 1977.

Meetings of Library of Congress Network Advisory Group and Network Technical Architecture Group as reported in the *Library of Congress Information Bulletin*:

"Network Representatives Meet at LC." (June 4, 1976):325.

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No. 28 *Gifts and Exchange Functions*

No. 29 *The Systems Function in ARL Libraries*

No. 30 *Support Staff and Student Assistants in ARL Libraries*

No. 31 *Allocation of Resources in Academic Libraries*

No. 32 *Preparation and Presentation of the Library Budget*

No. 33 *Integration of Nonprint Media*
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*NOTE: Items in these columns are not available from CLR.

CLR-Supported Projects Active in Fiscal 1977 (unaudited)

	FY 1977			
	Unpaid 6/30/76	Grants (Adjustments) ¹	Payments (Refunds)	Unpaid 6/30/77
American Association for State and Local History, Nashville, Tenn. Preparation of <i>Collection, Use and Care of Historical Photographs</i> (\$10,000—1972)	\$ 5,500	-0-	\$ 5,500	-0-
American Association of Law Libraries, Committee on Statistics, Washington, D. C. Survey of U. S. and Canadian law library resources (\$20,000—1968)	4,419	-0-	1,000	\$ 3,419
American Council of Learned Societies, New York, N.Y. Survey of Arabic, Persian, and Turkish manuscripts in U. S. libraries and other repositories (\$15,000—1975)	3,000	\$ (27)	2,973	-0-
American Library Association, Chicago, Ill. Consumers' handbook for public libraries (\$8,372—1975)	2,372	(237)	2,135	-0-
Revision of <i>Anglo-American Cataloging Rules</i> (\$111,432—1975)	49,431	22,228	49,431	22,228
Survey of compensation structures of academic librarians, 1975-76 (\$6,894—1975)	6,894	(65)	6,829	-0-
Etta Arntzen, Athens, Ga. Revision of <i>Guide to Art Reference Books</i> (\$8,000—1971)	1,600	-0-	-0-	1,600
Association of Research Libraries, Washington, D. C. Office of University Library Management Studies (\$81,136—1974; \$210,000—1975)	150,000	-0-	71,000	79,000
W. J. Barrow Research Laboratory, Inc., Richmond, Va. Research on preservation of books and other library materials. (\$240,000—1975)	34,985	37,000 (10,000)	36,940 (538)	25,583
Boston Theological Institute, Cambridge, Mass. ISSN's for theological serials (\$1,000—1975; \$1,200—1976)	1,200	-0-	-0-	1,200
College Entrance Examination Board, New York, N.Y. CEEB Office of Library Independent Study and Guidance Projects (\$50,000—1974; \$19,943—1976)	10,450	(5,255)	5,195	-0-

	FY 1977			
	Unpaid 6/30/76	Grants (Adjustments) ¹	Payments (Refunds)	Unpaid 6/30/77
Columbia University, New York, N.Y.				
Columbia University Libraries planning office (\$126,308 — 1971)	-0-	\$ (409)	\$ (409)	-0-
Consortium for Public Library Innovation, Tulsa, Ok. Support of the Consortium's research study group	-0-	10,930	7,200	\$ 3,730
Council-Administered Projects²				
Academic Library Development Program:				
Carnegie-Mellon University; refinement of manual	-0-	21,000	4,500	16,500
North Carolina Central University; for project coordinator	-0-	73,527	24,785	48,742
University of North Carolina/Charlotte; pilot project (\$47,046 — 1975)	\$ 14,046	(5,513)	11,000 (2,467)	-0-
University of Wisconsin — Parkside; refinement of manual	-0-	21,350	-0-	21,350
Academic Library Management Intern Program (\$100,000 — 1974; \$265,000 — 1975; \$110,000 — 1976)	130,385	(22,000)	103,086	5,299
1977-78	-0-	98,330		98,330
Advanced Study Program for Librarians (\$115,000 — 1975)	105,000	(20,000)	75,290	9,710
1977-78	-0-	73,092	50	73,042
CONSER project (\$250,000 — 1975)	139,094	-0-	82,043	57,051
Fellowship Program through September 1977	63,832	526	33,714	
1977-78	-0-	(13,258) 51,025 (6,100)	(1,385) 9,900	18,771 35,025
Library Service Enhancement Program (\$220,000 — 1976)	172,672	(16,262)	123,649	32,761
1977-78	-0-	194,857	17,577	177,280
Network Advisory Group meetings				
First meeting (\$3,250 — 1976)	490	(490)	-0-	-0-
Second meeting (\$2,750 — 1976)	2,750	(80)	2,670	-0-
Third meeting	-0-	3,141	3,141	-0-
Travel by U.S. librarians for purposes important to profession	-0-	3,583 (366)	2,663 (270)	824
Travel funds to enable leading foreign librarians to visit the U.S.	1,911	2,800 (1,397)	3,314	-0-
J. Periam Danton, Berkeley, Calif.				
Completion of supplement, 1966-75, of <i>Index to Festschriften in Librarianship</i>	-0-	500	400	100

	FY 1977			
	Unpaid 6/30/76	Grants (Adjustments) ¹	Payments (Refunds)	Unpaid 6/30/77
Suzanne Dodson, University of British Columbia, Vancouver. Guide to large collections in microform (\$1,950—1976)	\$ 1,450	-0-	\$ 1,450	-0-
Earlham College, Richmond, Ind. Periodical list for <i>Choice</i> (\$7,500—1975)	5,200	-0-	1,000	\$ 4,200
Eastern Michigan University, Ypsilanti, Mich. Project LOEX (\$41,969—1975)	28,369	\$ 4,765	20,400	12,734
International Council on Archives, Washington, D.C. ICA Secretariat (\$72,000—1975)	44,500	-0-	22,000	22,500
International Federation of Library Associations and Institutions, The Hague, Netherlands. Professional activities of the secretariat (\$174,000—1975)	152,014	-0-	49,000	103,014
International Office for Universal Bibliographic Control (\$70,000—1974; \$144,200—1975)	82,200	150,000	51,000	181,200
Iowa State University, Ames, Iowa. Mechanized indexing procedures applied to production of subject-enhanced keyword index	-0-	1,926	750	1,176
William V. Jackson, Nashville, Tenn. Study of Latin American Libraries (\$1,445—1976)	1,445	-0-	900	545
Library of Congress, Washington, D.C. COMARC project (\$106,132—1975)	13,632	55,000 (3,334)	18,815	46,483
Expenses for Fourth Assembly of State Librarians at LC, May 4-6, 1977	-0-	11,525 (1,363)	7,500	2,662
Integration of CONSER in national bibliographic service at LC (\$165,800—1975)	149,450	-0-	76,600	72,850
National Preservation Program				
Meeting of Ad Hoc Advisory Committee	-0-	5,960	285	5,675
Travel grant for conference	-0-	5,656	5,656	-0-
Survey for microform edition of <i>RAL</i> (\$12,200—1975)	2,000	-0-	-0-	2,000
Michigan State University, East Lansing, Mich. University extension library services directory (\$1,609—1971)	402	(300)	102	-0-

	Unpaid 6/30/76	FY 1977		Unpaid 6/30/77
		Grants (Adjustments) ¹	Payments (Refunds)	
MIDLNET, Green Bay, Wis. Toward salary of a technical advisor	-0-	\$ 22,778	-0-	\$ 22,778
Minnesota Higher Education Coordinating Board, St. Paul, Minn. For MINITEX—Pilot test of national serials location system	-0-	25,000	\$ 10,000	15,000
National Archives and Records Service, Washington, D.C. Partial support of meetings of ICA Committee on Archival Development and of regional rapporteurs	-0-	3,910 (833)	3,500 (423)	-0-
National Association of State Universities and Land Grant Colleges, Atlanta, Ga. Status report on libraries of historically black public colleges (\$2,500—1976)	\$ 500	-0-	500	-0-
National Endowment for the Humanities, Washington, D.C. University of Chicago Library Data Management System (matching grant)	-0-	200,000 (36,537)	163,463	-0-
National Library of Canada, Ottawa. To increase the library's ability to authenticate titles in CONSER	78,000	(78,000)	-0-	-0-
New England Board of Higher Education, Wellesley, Mass. Publication of NELINET system-use survey	-0-	3,235	3,235	-0-
The New York Public Library, New York, N.Y. Research support for "National Citizens Emergency Committee to Save our Public Libraries"	-0-	10,000	5,000	5,000
Ohio College Library Center, Columbus, Ohio. Development of on-line acquisition subsystem (\$124,250—1975)	58,250	-0-	58,250	-0-
Study of design of a nationwide library network, of functions of individual computerized nodes in such a network, and of future governance of OCLC	-0-	130,000 (8,000)	50,000	72,000
Organization of American States, Washington, D.C. Travel and report production costs of meeting to approve MARCAL	-0-	12,000	4,125	7,875

	FY 1977			Unpaid 6/30/77
	Unpaid 6/30/76	Grants (Adjustments) ¹	Payments (Refunds)	
Catherine M. Oukhow, Belgium. Stipend for work experience at Library of Congress	-0-	\$ 450	\$ 450	-0-
PTC Research Foundation, Concord, N.H. Conference on abstracting legal ar- ticles for computer storage and retrieval (\$5,250 — 1976)	\$ 2,250	-0-	2,250	-0-
Pennsylvania State University, Uni- versity Park, Pa. Assessment of impact of MRAP (\$31,509 — 1976)	24,509	-0-	21,000	\$ 3,509
William S. Pierce, Pennsylvania State University, State College, Pa. "Plan- ning the Library Interior" (\$3,000 — 1975)	500	-0-	-0-	500
Princeton University, Princeton, N.J. Microform service development	-0-	10,000	1,250	8,750
Frank Rodgers, Portland State Univer- sity, Portland, Ore. Manual of British government publications (\$4,300 — 1976)	300	-0-	300	-0-
Southeastern Library Network, At- lanta, Ga. Training librarians to partici- pate in SOLINET (\$10,000 — 1974)	1,200	-0-	1,200	-0-
Stockton State College, Pomona, N.J. Innovative use of <i>Books for College Li- braries II</i>	-0-	5,150	2,000	3,150
Syracuse University, Syracuse, N.Y. Improved access to books by augmenta- tion of MARC records (\$76,615 — 1976)	51,615	-0-	15,000	36,615
University of Chicago, Chicago, Ill. Library Data Management System (\$350,000 — 1975)	100,000	-0-	100,000	-0-
Fellowship program for holders of non- library Ph.D. degrees (\$103,000 — 1974)	3,250	-0-	-0-	3,250
University of Connecticut, Storrs, Conn. New England Academic Li- brarians' Writing Seminar	-0-	20,610	6,074	14,536
University of Illinois Law Library, Champaign, Ill. On-line computer re- ference service (\$1,080 — 1976)	330	-0-	330	-0-

	FY 1977			Unpaid 6/30/77
	Unpaid 6/30/76	Grants (Adjustments) ¹	Payments (Refunds)	
University of North Carolina, Chapel Hill, N.C. Administration of ANSI Committee Z-39 through April 1976 (\$14,000 — 1975)	\$ 1,710	\$ (1,710)	-0-	-0-
Through Dec. 1977 (\$29,649 — 1976)	29,649	-0-	\$ 20,000	\$ 9,649
Through Jan. 1978 (\$23,719 — 1976)	23,719	-0-	-0-	23,719
University of the State of New York, Albany, N.Y. State Library study of state government information needs (\$25,000 — 1974)	4,000	-0-	-0-	4,000
Vanderbilt University, Nashville, Tenn. Joint University Libraries model research and development unit (\$171,107 — 1969; \$89,465 — 1972)	4,760	-0-	4,760	-0-
Wabash College, Crawfordsville, Ind. For its College Library Program (matching grant) (\$50,000 — 1970)	2,500	-0-	2,500	-0-
Washington State Library, Olympia, Wash. Evaluation of circulation subsystem alternatives of the Washington Library Network	-0-	15,000 (3,371)	11,629	-0-
Washington University Libraries, St. Louis, Mo. To develop internal financial auditing procedures for university libraries (\$10,000 — 1976)	6,000	-0-	592	5,408
Western Interstate Commission for Higher Education, Boulder, Colo. Design of a western interstate bibliographic network (\$79,325 — 1975)	9,325	-0-	9,325	-0-
TOTALS	1,783,060	1,306,854	1,438,176	1,651,738
Less adjustments/refunds		(234,907)	(5,492)	(229,415)
	<u>\$1,783,060</u>	<u>\$1,071,947</u>	<u>\$1,432,684</u>	<u>\$1,422,323</u>

¹Unused portion restored to fund balance.

²See also "Schedule of Appropriations for Council-Administered Projects," p. 65.

Schedule of Appropriations for Council—Administered Projects (unaudited)

June 30, 1977

	Appropriated Balance 6/30/76	Appropriations (Restored to Funds)	Awards (Restored to Appropriations)	Project Costs Paid	Appropriated Balance 6/30/77
Academic Library Development Program 1976-77	\$ 46,786	\$ (42,831)		\$ 3,955	-0-
Continuation 1977-78	200,000	48,343	\$115,877	1,095	\$131,371
Academic Library Management Intern Program 1974-77	19,160			14,030	5,130
Continuation 1977-78	110,000	12,000	98,330	10,100	13,570
Continuation 1978-79		80,000		72	79,928
Advanced Study Program For Librarians 1977-78	110,000	2,000 (20,000)	73,092	8,674	10,234
College Library Program		100,000			100,000
Committee for the Coordina- tion of National Bibliographic Control 1975	6,342			6,342	-0-
Continuation 1976	25,000			20,291	4,709
Computer output microfilm study	14,756			10,571	4,185
Conversion of Serials— CONSER	10,597			1,293	9,304
Fellowship Program 1977-78	100,000	(42,748)	51,025	3,227	3,000
Continuation 1978-79		80,000		53	79,947
Library Service Enhancement Program 1976-77	14,228	(6,935)		7,293	-0-
Continuation 1977-78	210,000	12,000 (13,584)	194,857	5,337	8,222
Network Technical Advisory Group		20,000		6,096	13,904
Study of significant private libraries in England	3,021	(2,674)		347	-0-
Travel (foreign) by U. S. librarians for purposes important to profession	1,700	4,700	2,383 (136)		4,153
Travel (other) by U. S. librar- ians for purposes important to profession	1,973		1,200 (230)		1,003
Travel (U. S.) by foreign librarians		2,892	2,800 (5)		97
Totals	873,563	361,935	539,564	98,776	468,757
Less restorations		(128,772)	(371)		468,757
	<u>\$873,563</u>	<u>\$233,163</u>	<u>\$539,193</u>	<u>\$98,776</u>	<u>\$468,757</u>

Council on Library Resources, Inc.

Opinion of Independent Accountants

August 24, 1977

To The Board of Directors of
Council of Library Resources, Inc.

We have examined the balance sheet of the Council on Library Resources, Inc. (Council) as of June 30, 1977, and the related statements of activity under restricted Ford Foundation grant, of functional expenses and of changes in cash and investments for the three year period then ended. Our examination was made in accordance with generally accepted auditing standards and accordingly included such tests of the accounting records and such other auditing procedures as we considered necessary in the circumstances.

The Council's operations are financed primarily through grants from the Ford Foundation. Effective July 1, 1974, the Council received a new grant of \$6,000,000 for continuation of its program for a three year period. The Council considers its "business cycle" as the three years coinciding with the term of the grant. Accordingly, as described in Note 2 to the financial statements, the results of activity and changes in cash and investments are presented in the accompanying financial statements for the three year period from the inception of the present grant, July 1, 1974.

In our opinion, the financial statements examined by us present fairly on the basis described above the financial position of the Council on Library Resources, Inc. at June 30, 1977, and the results of its activity and the changes in cash and investments for the three year period then ended.

Price Waterhouse & Co.
Washington, D. C.

Council on Library Resources, Inc.

Balance Sheet

June 30, 1977

Assets

Cash	\$ 166,809
Investments	792,104
Accrued royalties (Note 3)	1,065
Grant receivable from The Ford Foundation (Note 2)	1,000,000
Other receivables	2,016
Prepaid expenses and deposits	<u>2,603</u>
Total assets	<u>\$1,964,597</u>

Liabilities and Restricted Grant

Grants, fellowships and contracts payable	\$1,422,323
Co-sponsored grants payable	1,132
Accounts payable and accrued salaries, taxes and employee benefits	<u>39,044</u>
Total liabilities	<u>1,462,499</u>
Restricted Ford Foundation grant	
Appropriated	\$468,757
Unappropriated	<u>33,341</u>
Total liabilities and restricted grant	<u>\$1,964,597</u>

Council on Library Resources, Inc.

Statement of Activity
Under Restricted Ford Foundation Grant
For the Three Year Period Ending June 30, 1977 (Note 2)

Grant awarded (of which \$5,000,000 has been received) (Note 2)	\$6,000,000
Investment income	212,909
Royalty income	<u>11,720</u>
Total support	<u>6,224,629</u>
Expenses	
Program services	5,494,646
Administrative services	<u>714,079</u>
Total expenses	<u>6,208,725</u>
Excess of support over expenses to June 30, 1977, before cumulative effect of a change in accounting method	15,904
Cumulative effect on prior periods (to June 30, 1974) of applying retroactively the new method of accounting for grant expense	58,593
Previous restricted Ford Foundation grants unexpended at June 30, 1974	<u>427,601</u>
Restricted Ford Foundation grant at June 30, 1977	<u>\$ 502,098</u>

Council on Library Resources, Inc.

Statement of Functional Expenses
For the Three Year Period Ending June 30, 1977

	Program Services									
	Automation, networks, standardization, and national library services	Libraries and their users	Management	Microforms and preservation	Professional development	International	General	Total	Administrative services	Total
Grants and contracts	\$2,620,564	\$546,445	\$414,432	\$280,929	\$496,922	\$631,575	\$142,751	\$5,133,618		\$5,133,618
Fellowships					176,957			176,957		176,957
Council-administered projects	80,268	24,231	11,217	26,783	82,135	5,431		230,065		230,065
Less: Adjustments resulting from excess allocations of grants and fellowships	(635,180)	(21,781)	(12,623)	(50,660)	(103,769)	(6,254)	(48,738)	(879,005)		(879,005)
	2,065,652	548,895	413,026	257,052	652,245	630,752	94,013	4,661,635		4,661,635
Program Support										
Compensation and employee benefits	414,590	27,117	20,689	153,632	45,646	20,649	16,838	699,161	\$428,577	1,127,738
Consultant fees	17,600	11,563	9,125	150	11,980	12,922	4,336	67,676		67,676
Travel and meetings	42,703	2,679	1,697	5,225	4,160	1,758	380	58,602	41,229	99,831
Other	6,509	175	8	476	395	6	3	7,572		7,572
Audit and legal fees									28,576	28,576
Rent									99,929	99,929
Equipment rental and furniture									13,586	13,586
Printing and duplication									29,861	29,861
Office and other expense									72,321	72,321
	<u>\$2,547,054</u>	<u>\$590,429</u>	<u>\$444,545</u>	<u>\$416,535</u>	<u>\$714,426</u>	<u>\$666,087</u>	<u>\$115,570</u>	<u>\$5,494,646</u>	<u>\$714,079</u>	<u>\$6,208,725</u>

Council on Library Resources, Inc.

Statement of Changes in Cash and Investments

For the Three Year Period Ending June 30, 1977

Cash receipts

Receipts from The Ford Foundation	\$5,000,000
Receipts from co-sponsors	39,300
Income from investments and royalties	235,221
Grant and fellowship refunds	<u>22,985</u>
	<u>5,297,506</u>

Cash disbursements

Program expense	5,430,404
Administrative expense	<u>726,905</u>
	<u>6,157,309</u>
Excess of cash disbursements over cash receipts	(859,803)
Decrease in accrued interest	(8,724)
Cash and investments, July 1, 1974	<u>1,827,440</u>
Cash and investments, June 30, 1977	<u>\$ 958,913</u>

Notes to Financial Statements

June 30, 1977

1. Organization

The Council on Library Resources, Inc. (Council) is a nonprofit organization incorporated under the laws of the District of Columbia in 1956 for the purpose of promoting library research. The Council's operations are financed primarily through grants from The Ford Foundation. Effective July 1, 1974, the Council received a new grant of \$6,000,000 for continuation of its program for a three year period. The Council conducts its work through directly administered programs as well as grants to and contracts with other appropriate organizations or individuals.

The Council is a private operating foundation and is exempt from Federal income tax under Internal Revenue Code section 501(c)(3).

2. Summary of Significant Accounting Policies and Changes in Accounting Methods

The Council considers as its "business cycle" the three years coinciding with the term of the grant from The Ford Foundation. Consequently, the results of activity and the changes in cash and investments are presented for the period from the effective date of the present grant, July 1, 1974.

In years prior to 1974, the Council reported its financial affairs on an individual year by year basis without regard to this three year "business cycle." Under the new reporting, the full amount of The Ford Foundation grant for the three year period is recognized as revenue as of the effective date of the grant. Any grant funds not expended or committed by the Council within the three year term of the grant must, in accordance with the grant agreement, be returned to The Ford Foundation. However, Ford has subsequently modified the terms of the original grant to allow expenditure of the remaining funds through 1979.

Grants, contracts, and fellowships are recorded as expense when the recipients are notified that they are to receive the funds. The Council formerly followed the policy of recognizing grant and contract expense when the funds for the specific purposes were appropriated by the Board of Directors. The new method has been adopted to more properly reflect the liability created when the recipients have been notified of their selection. The effect of the change is to decrease grant and contract expense by \$410,008 for the three year period ended June 30, 1977. The cumulative effect of the change in the method of recognizing grant and contract expense at July 1, 1974 of \$58,593 is included in the accompanying statements to give effect to the retroactive application of the new method.

Purchases of office furniture and equipment are recorded as an expense in the year acquired.

3. Royalties

The Council receives royalties from the sale of a publication entitled *Handbook of Data Processing for Libraries*. The Council also receives royalties under an agreement relating to the publication and sale of a book entitled *Economics of Academic Libraries*. Both of these publications were developed under the Council's sponsorship financed by The Ford Foundation and accordingly royalties are considered restricted funds.

4. Retirement Plan

Employees are eligible for participation in the Council's retirement annuity program, which is administered through the TIAA/CREF insurance companies. Individual contracts issued under the plan provide for full and immediate vesting of both the Council's and employees' contributions. The Council's contribution amounted to \$110,000 for the three year period ended June 30, 1977.

5. Commitments

The Council leases office space under a lease expiring November 30, 1977 providing for minimum annual rentals of approximately \$35,000.

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Acronyms Used In This Report

AACR	Anglo-American Cataloging Rules	MIDLNET	Midwest Region Library Network
AIDS	Automated Identification Systems	MINITEX	Minnesota Interlibrary Telecommunications Exchange
ALA	American Library Association	MRAP	Management Review and Analysis Program
ALDP	Academic Library Development Program	NAG	Network Advisory Group
ANSI	American National Standards Institute	NARS	National Archives and Records Service
ARL	Association of Research Libraries	NCLIS	National Commission on Libraries and Information Science
BALLOTS	Bibliographic Automation of Large Library Operations using a Time-sharing System	NEH	National Endowment for the Humanities
BCL	Books for College Libraries	NELINET	New England Library Information Network
CCNBC	Committee for the Coordination of National Bibliographic Control	NSF	National Science Foundation
CEEB	College Entrance Examination Board	NTAG	Network Technical Architecture Group
CLEP	College Level Examination Program	OAS	Organization of American States
CLR	Council on Library Resources, Inc.	OCLC	Ohio College Library Center
COM	Computer Output Microfilm	OCR	Optical Character Recognition
COMARC	Cooperative MARC	OMS	Office of University Library Management Studies
CONSER	Conversion of Serials	ORBIT	On-Line Retrieval of Bibliographic Information — Time-shared
FID	Federation Internationale de Documentation	PLATO	Programmed Logic for Automated Teaching Operations
ICA	International Council on Archives	RAL	Register of Additional Locations
IFLA	International Federation of Library Associations and Institutions	SPEC	Systems and Procedures Exchange Center
INCOLSA	Indiana Cooperative Library Service Agency	UBC	Universal Bibliographic Control
ISBN	International Standard Book Number	UNCC	University of North Carolina at Charlotte
ISSN	International Standard Serial Number	UNESCO	United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization
LC	Library of Congress	UNIMARC	Universal MARC
LOEX	Library Orientation/ instruction Exchange	WICHE	Western Interstate Commission for Higher Education
MARC	Machine-Readable Cataloging	WILCO	Western Interstate Library Coordinating Organization
MARCAL	Manual de catalogación mecanizada para América Latina	WLN	Washington Library Network
MEDLARS	Medical Literature Analysis and Retrieval System		

